

Water and Nutrient Balances of Upper Klamath Lake, Water Years 1992–2018

Prepared for

Klamath Tribes
Natural Resources Department

by

Jeffrey D. Walker, Ph.D.
Walker Environmental Research LLC

and

Jacob Kann, Ph.D.
Aquatic Ecosystem Sciences LLC

May 2022

Appendices

- A Precipitation and Evaporation Datasets**
- B Annual and Seasonal Variations in Tributary Nutrient Species Concentrations**
- C Flow and Nutrient Load Calculations for Pump Areas and Gauged Tributaries**
- D Annual and Seasonal Variations in Mass Balance Terms**
- E Water and Nutrient Mass Balance Summaries**
- F Inflow/Outflow Total Phosphorus Loading Dynamics**
- G Trends in Flow, Load, and Concentrations of Mass Balance Terms**

Appendix A

Precipitation and Evaporation Datasets

Table A1 Meteorological data sources and stations

Figure A1 Map of meteorological stations

Table A2 Primary and secondary stations used for filling precipitation datasets

Figure A2 Monthly precipitation by station

Figure A3 Monthly precipitation relationships by region

Figure A4 Final monthly and annual precipitation

Figure A5 Monthly evaporation by station

Figure A6 Monthly evaporation relationships

Figure A7 Final monthly and annual evaporation

Table A1: Meteorological data sources and stations

Region	Data Source	Code	Description	Station ID	Latitude	Longitude	Period (WY)
North	AgriMet	AGKO	Agency Lake Ranch, Oregon	AGKO	42.56527	-121.98250	2000-2018
North	GHCND	CHIL	OR CHILOQUIN 12 NW	USC00351574	42.70360	-121.99530	1992-2018
South	AgriMet	KFLO	Klamath Falls, Oregon	KFLO	42.16472	-121.75500	1999-2018
South	GHCND	KF2	OR KLAMATH FALLS 2 SSW	USC00354506	42.20080	-121.78140	1992-2001
South	GHCND	KFA	OR KLAMATH FALLS INTL AP	USW00094236	42.14690	-121.72420	1998-2018
South	GSOD	KFA	KLAMATH FALLS INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT, OR US	72589594236	42.14694	-121.72417	1992-2018

References

- AgriMet USBR (2022a). AgriMet: Pacific Northwest Cooperative Agricultural Weather Network [website]. <http://www.usbr.gov/pn/agrimet/> [accessed January 5, 2022]
- GHCND Menne, M.J., Durre, I., Korzeniewski, B., McNeill, S., Thomas, K., Yin, X., Anthony, S., Ray, R., Vose, R.S., Gleason, B.E., and T.G. Houston (2012). Global Historical Climatology Network - Daily (GHCN-Daily), Version 3. NOAA National Climatic Data Center. doi:10.7289/V5D21VHZ [access January 5, 2022].
- GSOD National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI) (2022). Global Surface Summary of the Day – GSOD. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/metadata/geoportal/rest/metadata/item/gov.noaa.ncdc:C00516/html> [accessed January 5, 2022]

Figure A1: Map of meteorological stations

Table A2: Primary and secondary stations used for filling precipitation datasets

Region	Period	Primary Station	Secondary Stations
North	1991-2018	GHCND:CHIL	AgriMet:AGKO, GHCND:KF2, GSOD:KFA
South	1991-1998	GHCND:KF2	GSOD:KFA
South	1998-2018	GHCND:KFA	AgriMet:KFLO

Figure A2: Monthly precipitation by station

Southern Stations (near Klamath Falls)

Northern Stations (near Agency Lake)

Figure A3: Monthly precipitation relationships by region

Figure A4: Final monthly and annual precipitation

Figure A5: Monthly evaporation by station

Figure A6: Monthly evaporation relationships

Figure A7: Final monthly and annual evaporation

Appendix B

Annual and Seasonal Variations in Tributary Nutrient Species Concentrations

Figure B1 Annual and seasonal variations in nutrient species concentrations at tributary monitoring stations

Figure B1: Annual and seasonal variations in nutrient species concentrations at tributary monitoring stations

Description: Monthly and annual geometric mean time series of concentrations for each major sampling station

Parameters:

TP	Total Phosphorus
SRP	Soluble Reactive Phosphorus
TN	Total Nitrogen
InorgN	Inorganic Nitrogen (NH4N + NO32N)

Stations:

Sevenmile Canal @ Dike Road
Wood River @ Weed Road
Wood River @ Dike Road
Sprague River
Williamson River
Lake Outlet

Panels:

A	Timeseries of monthly geomean and raw samples colored by data source
B	Timeseries of annual geomean computed using sample concentrations from all data sources
C	Timeseries of monthly geomean and samples concentrations grouped by month

Note: Sample data were constrained to the maximum detection limits over the period of record:
 (TP = 18 ppb, SRP = 3 ppb, TN = 100 ppb, InorgN = 20 ppb)
 Monthly and annual geometric means computed directly from sample concentration data
 Results for TP and TN may be different from those shown in the main report or other appendices, which are based on the load estimates computed for the mass balance (see Appendix C)

Site: Sevenmile Canal @ Dike Rd
Parameter: TP

- Data Source
- Klamath Tribes
 - KBRT
 - USBR
 - PacifiCorp/USBR
 - Geomean

Site: Sevenmile Canal @ Dike Rd
Parameter: SRP

- Data Source
- Klamath Tribes
 - KBRT
 - USBR
 - PacifiCorp/USBR
 - Geomean

Site: Sevenmile Canal @ Dike Rd
Parameter: TN

Site: Sevenmile Canal @ Dike Rd
Parameter: InorgN

Site: Wood River @ Weed Rd
Parameter: TP

- Data Source
- Klamath Tribes
 - KBRT
 - USBR
 - PacifiCorp/USBR
 - Geomean

Site: Wood River @ Weed Rd
Parameter: SRP

- Data Source
- Klamath Tribes
 - KBRT
 - USBR
 - PacifiCorp/USBR
 - Geomean

Site: Wood River @ Weed Rd
Parameter: TN

- Data Source
- Klamath Tribes
 - KBRT
 - USBR
 - PacifiCorp/USBR
 - Geomean

Site: Wood River @ Weed Rd
Parameter: InorgN

Site: Wood River @ Dike Rd
Parameter: TP

Site: Wood River @ Dike Rd
Parameter: SRP

- Data Source
- Klamath Tribes
 - KBRT
 - USBR
 - PacifiCorp/USBR
 - Geomean

Site: Wood River @ Dike Rd
Parameter: TN

Site: Wood River @ Dike Rd
Parameter: InorgN

Data Source

- Klamath Tribes
- KBRT
- USBR
- PacifiCorp/USBR
- Geomean

Site: Sprague River
Parameter: TP

Site: Sprague River
Parameter: SRP

Site: Sprague River
Parameter: TN

Site: Sprague River
Parameter: InorgN

Site: Williamson River
Parameter: TP

- Data Source
- Klamath Tribes
 - KBRT
 - USBR
 - PacifiCorp/USBR
 - Geomean

Site: Williamson River
Parameter: SRP

- Data Source
- Klamath Tribes
 - KBRT
 - USBR
 - PacifiCorp/USBR
 - Geomean

Site: Williamson River
Parameter: TN

Site: Williamson River
Parameter: InorgN

Site: Lake Outlet
Parameter: TP

Site: Lake Outlet
Parameter: SRP

Site: Lake Outlet
Parameter: TN

Site: Lake Outlet
Parameter: InorgN

Appendix C

Flow and Nutrient Load Calculations for Pump Areas and Gauged Tributaries

Table C1 Drainage areas and average discharge concentrations of pumped areas

Figure C1 Map of pumped areas

Figure C2 Estimation of daily flows at Wood River and Sevenmile Creek stations

Figure C3 Algorithm for estimating loads using daily flow and biweekly concentration data

Figure C4 Diagnostics from load calculations at gauged tributary stations and lake outflow

Figure C5 Comparison of regression-based and linear interpolation load estimation methods

Table C1: Drainage areas and average discharge concentrations of pumped areas

Area	WQ Station	Drainage Area		Outflow Concentrations ¹		Notes
		acres	km ²	TP (ppb)	TN (ppb)	
Agency Lake Ranch						Restoration began in 1998, used by USBR for water storage
Agency Lake Ranch	ALR / TUPU	11,450	46.4	272	1,596	
Williamson River Delta Preserve (WRDP)						Converted to restored wetland over 1997-2000 ²
Tulana (west)	WRPU	3,623	14.7	975	3,501	Permanently inundated in Oct 2007
Goose Bay (east)		2,015	8.2	N/A	N/A	Permanently inundated in Oct 2008, no samples collected
Total WRDP		5,638	22.9	975	3,501	
Ungauged Areas						
Algoma	ALG / BSPU	1,168	4.7	446	2,468	
Shady Pine	SPPU	385	1.6	330	2,296	
Cove Point	HMPU	348	1.4	141	678	
McCormack	MCPU	249	1	321	1,197	
Caledonia	CAPU	2,136	8.7	186	1,764	Temporarily inundated ³ , June 2006 - Sept 2007
Wocus	WOPU	3,789	15.3	185	4,169	
Ball		783	3.2	N/A	N/A	No samples collected
Odessa	ODPU	398	1.6	79	1,627	
Total Ungauged Areas		9,256	37.5	225	2,893	Area-weighted mean of ungauged areas

¹ Geometric means of Klamath Tribes sampling data, 1991-1998 (Kann and Walker, 1999; Walker et al., 2012)

² 750 acres remained under lease for alfalfa production after 2000 (Megan Skinner (USFWS) personal communication)

³ Caledonia Marsh was unintentionally flooded beginning June 7, 2006 (Lindenberg and Wood, 2009). The levee was repaired and the parcel drained and reverted back to farmland in 2007 (assumed complete by end of the water year).

Figure C1: Map of pumped areas

Note: Wood River Ranch and Thomas parcels discharge to the Wood River and Sevenmile Canal. Therefore, loads from these areas are accounted for in the respective gauged tributary inflow terms, and are **not** included among the pumped areas inflow terms.

Figure C2: Estimation of daily flows at Wood River and Sevenmile Creek stations

Description: Flow data and regression models used to estimate continuous daily flows at Wood River and Sevenmile Canal stations

Stations:

Label	Description
Sevenmile@Dike	Sevenmile Canal at Dike Road
Wood@Weed	Wood River at Weed Road
Wood@Dike	Wood River at Dike Road

Panels:

A	Timeseries of discrete and continuous flow measurements, and final daily timeseries
B	Linear regression models used to fill discrete (e.g., biweekly) flow measurements
C	List of stations for each data source
D	Summary of methods used to estimate daily flows over the period of record

Wood River @ Weed Rd.

Wood River @ Weed Rd.

Flow Measurements and Final Daily Timeseries

Regression of Wood@Weed (KT) against Wood@Weed (KBRT)
Period: Sep 1998 – Nov 2011

Regression of Wood@Weed (KT) against Wood@Dike (USGS)
Period: Aug 2013 – Sep 2018

Data Source	Site ID	Period (WY)	Count
KT	WR3000	1994–2019	466
KBRT	WOWR,WRWR	1991–2012	6914
USBR	WOWR	1991–1996	45

Methods

1991–1997: KBRT daily data

1997–1998: Linear interpolation of discrete KT data

1998–2011: Interpolate biweekly KT data using residuals of regression against KBRT data

2011–2013: Linear interpolation of biweekly KT data

2013–2018: Interpolate biweekly KT data using residuals of regression against daily USGS Wood@Dike data

Wood River @ Dike Rd.

Flow Measurements and Final Daily Timeseries

Regression of Wood@Dike (KT/USBR) against Wood@Weed (Final)
 Period: Oct 1991 – Sep 2018

Data Source	Site ID	Period (WY)	Count
KT	WR4000	1993–2019	514
KBRT	WRDIKE,WRDR	2002–2005	982
USBR	WODR	1991–1996	45
USGS	11504115	2013–2020	2618

Methods

- 1991–2013** Interpolate biweekly KT/USBR data using residuals of final Wood@Weed daily flows
- 2003–2005** KBRT daily data
- 2005–2013** Interpolate biweekly KT/USBR data using residuals of final Wood@Weed daily flows
- 2013–2018** USGS daily data

Sevenmile Canal @ Dike Rd.

Flow Measurements and Final Daily Timeseries

Regression of Sevenmile@Dike (KT/USBR) against Wood@Weed (Final)
 Period: Oct 1991 – Sep 2018

Data Source	Site ID	Period (WY)	Count
KT	WR5000	1992–2019	396
KBRT	SMDIKE,SMDR	2002–2007	1206
USBR	7MCA	1992–1996	28
USGS	11504290	2017–2020	1246

Methods

- 1991–2013** Interpolate biweekly KT/USBR data using residuals of final Wood@Weed daily flows
- 2003–2006** KBRT daily data
- 2007–2017** Interpolate biweekly KT/USBR data using residuals of final Wood@Weed daily flows
- 2017–2018** USGS daily data

Figure C3: Algorithm for estimating loads using daily flow and biweekly concentration data

Description: At each station, daily nutrient loads were computed using continuous daily flows and concentrations. The daily concentrations were estimated by interpolating between sampled concentrations (often collected at biweekly intervals) using a linear regression model that captures the seasonality, flow-dependence, and long-term trend of concentrations at each station. Between each pair of samples, the concentrations were interpolated using the residuals of the regression model predictions. As a result, this method accounts for the serial correlation of model residuals over time, and also ensures that the final daily concentrations are equal to the observed concentrations on each sampling date. The results are similar to a simple linear interpolation of sampled concentrations, but by using the regression model predictions this method can better estimate changes in between samples associated with short-term variations in flow (i.e., storm events). The references below provide additional information about how this method and its applications.

Algorithm: 1. Fit linear regression to sample concentrations based on flow (Q), change in flow (Q_{deriv}), decimal year (Y), and julian day in radians (j)

$$\ln(C) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln Q + \beta_2 (\ln Q)^2 + \beta_3 (\ln Q)^3 + \beta_4 Q_{deriv} + \beta_5 Y + \beta_6 Y^2 + \beta_7 \cos(j) + \beta_8 \sin(j) + \beta_9 \cos(2j) + \beta_{10} \sin(2j)$$

where: C = concentration (ppb)

Q = flow (hm^3/d)

$Q_{deriv} = \ln(Q[t] / Q[t-1])$ (or zero if either flow is zero)

Y = year + Jday / 365.25 (decimal year; e.g., June 1, 2001 = 2001.414)

j = $2 * \pi * \text{Jday} / 365.25$ (Julian day in radians)

Jday = Julian day (1 = Jan 1, 2 = Jan 2, ...)

2. Compute predicted concentration (C_{pred}) for each date (t) using fitted linear regression and adjust for log-transformation bias

$$C_{pred}[t] = f(Q[t], Q_{deriv}[t], Y[t], j[t])$$

3. Compute log-based residual based on observed (C_{obs}) and predicted (C_{pred}) concentrations on each sample date (t^*)

$$\ln(C_{resid})[t^*] = \ln\left(\frac{C_{obs}[t^*]}{C_{pred}[t^*]}\right)$$

4. Linearly interpolate log-transformed residuals between sample dates (t^*) to generate continuous residual timeseries for all dates (t)

$$\ln(C_{resid})[t] = \text{interplinear}(\ln(C_{resid})[t^*], t)$$

5. Compute final daily concentrations (C_{final}) by adding daily log-transformed residuals (C_{resid}) to predicted concentrations (C_{pred}) on each date (t)

$$C_{final}[t] = C_{pred}[t] \cdot e^{\ln(C_{resid})[t]}$$

6. Compute final daily loads (L_{final}) by multiply daily flows (Q) by final daily concentrations (C_{final})

$$L_{final}[t] = Q[t] \cdot C_{final}[t]$$

Figure C3: Algorithm for estimating loads using daily flow and biweekly concentration data

Example: The following figure shows a) the sampled concentrations (C_{obs}), linearly interpolated concentrations (C_{linear}), predicted concentrations based on the linear regression model (C_{pred}), and the final daily concentrations (C_{final}), and b) the interpolated model residuals, which are computed as the ratio of the observed and predicted concentrations. The final daily concentrations (C_{final} ; orange line in top panel) are computed by multiplying the model predictions (C_{pred} ; purple line in top panel) by the interpolated residuals ($\exp(\ln C_{resid})$; gray line in bottom panel) per Step 5 above.

Term: Sprague | Period: 1997-01-28 to 1997-07-22

References: Walker, W.W. and K.E. Havens (2003). Development and Application of a Phosphorus Mass Balance Model for Lake Istokpoga, Florida. *Lake and Reservoir Management* 19(1): 79-91. Available online at http://www.wwwalker.net/pdf/istokpoga_2003.pdf

Walker, W.W. (2004). Long-Term Water Quality Database for Onondaga Lake Monitoring Program, prepared for Department of Water Environment Protection, Onondaga County, NY. March 30, 2004. Available online at <http://www.wwwalker.net/onondaga>

Walker, W.W. (1996). Simplified procedures for eutrophication assessment and prediction: User manual, Chapter 2 FLUX. Prepared for U.S. Army Corp of Engineers, Water Operations Technical Support Program, Instruction Report W-96-2. Available online at <http://www.wwwalker.net/bathtub>

Walker, W.W. (2002). Long-Term Monitoring of Watersheds: Statistical Models & Examples. Presented at "Science to Support Nutrient-Management Decisions Related to Hypoxia in the Northern Gulf of Mexico in the Mississippi River Basin", St. Louis, October 2002. Available online at http://www.wwwalker.net/pdf/hypoxia_st_louis_oct2002.pdf

Asarian, E., Kann, J., Walker, W.W. (2009). Multi-Year Nutrient Budget Dynamics for Iron Gate and Copco Reservoirs, California. Prepared for Karuk Tribe, Department of Natural Resources, December 2009.

Walker, J. D., J. Kann, and W.W. Walker (2015). Spatial and temporal nutrient loading dynamics in the Sprague River Basin, Oregon. Prepared by Aquatic Ecosystem Sciences, J. D. Walker, and W. W. Walker for the Klamath Tribes Natural Resources Department. 73p. + appendices.

Figure C4: Diagnostics from load calculations at gauged tributary stations and lake outflow

Description: Daily computed loads and concentrations generated from daily load estimation algorithm

Terms:

Label	Description
Sevenmile@Dike	Sevenmile Canal at Dike Road
Wood@Weed	Wood River at Weed Road
Wood@Dike	Wood River at Dike Road
Sprague	Sprague River
Williamson	Williamson River
Lake Outflow	Lake Outflow (Link River)

Panels:

A	Daily flows and loads, points denote values on sampling dates
B	Sample concentrations (points), regression predictions (gray line), and daily estimated concentrations generated by linear interpolation of regression residuals (orange line)
C	Scatterplot of observed vs. predicted concentrations. Blue line is linear regression trendline, dashed line is 1:1 line of equality
D	Scatterplot of observed and predicted concentrations vs. flow and day of the year (seasonal variation)
E	Scatterplots of log-transformed residual concentrations vs date, predicted concentration and day of year
F	Summary statistics of linear regression model
G	Regression coefficient estimates and p-values

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Sevenmile | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Sevenmile | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

• Observed
• Predicted

Term tribs_7mile_dike
Parameter TP
Samples 624
R² 0.452
Residual Std. Err. 0.321
Residual DOF 613

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	-1266	0.1719
q_deriv	0.0148	0.3439
dyear	1.267	0.1705
dyear2	-0.0003157	0.1707
cos_2t	0.1125	< 0.0001
sin_2t	0.1013	< 0.0001

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	-0.3919	< 0.0001
sin_t	-0.006343	0.7419
log_q3	0.003463	0.0072
log_q2	0.05957	0.0004
log_q	0.2484	< 0.0001

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Wood@Weed | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Wood@Weed | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

• Observed
• Predicted

Term tribs_wood_weed
Parameter TP
Samples 735
R² 0.106
Residual Std. Err. 0.144
Residual DOF 724

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	1201	0.0025
q_deriv	0.5874	< 0.0001
dyear	-1.193	0.0026
dyear2	0.0002973	0.0026
cos_2t	0.01391	0.0785
sin_2t	0.0252	0.0012

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	0.006636	0.5358
sin_t	0.02124	0.0091
log_q3	0.02995	0.3222
log_q2	0.1181	0.1517
log_q	0.0941	0.1353

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Wood@Dike | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Wood@Dike | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

• Observed
• Predicted

Term tribs_wood_dike
Parameter TP
Samples 712
R² 0.246
Residual Std. Err. 0.21
Residual DOF 701

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	2173	0.0002
q_deriv	0.2038	0.1272
dyear	-2.157	0.0002
dyear2	0.0005364	0.0002
cos_2t	0.01845	0.1098
sin_2t	-0.004323	0.7031

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	-0.0989	< 0.0001
sin_t	0.1142	< 0.0001
log_q3	0.01538	0.4769
log_q2	0.08355	0.2106
log_q	0.1261	0.0100

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Sprague | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Sprague | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

• Observed
• Predicted

Term tribs_sprague
Parameter TP
Samples 621
R² 0.582
Residual Std. Err. 0.252
Residual DOF 610

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	-289.1	0.7051
q_deriv	0.1493	0.2592
dyear	0.2977	0.6960
dyear2	-7.558e-05	0.6908
cos_2t	0.07203	< 0.0001
sin_2t	-0.002656	0.8673

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	0.1587	< 0.0001
sin_t	0.2438	< 0.0001
log_q3	-0.07937	< 0.0001
log_q2	0.1879	< 0.0001
log_q	0.1832	< 0.0001

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Williamson | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Williamson | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

• Observed
• Predicted

Term tribs_williamson
Parameter TP
Samples 617
R² 0.224
Residual Std. Err. 0.178
Residual DOF 606

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	924.8	0.0902
q_deriv	0.3096	0.0325
dyear	-0.9153	0.0927
dyear2	0.0002275	0.0936
cos_2t	0.03611	0.0007
sin_2t	0.05239	< 0.0001

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	0.02161	0.0655
sin_t	0.04798	0.0018
log_q3	-0.04201	0.0786
log_q2	0.2473	0.0024
log_q	-0.2586	0.0016

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Lake Outflow | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Lake Outflow | Parameter: Total Phosphorus

• Observed
• Predicted

Term outflow
Parameter TP
Samples 669
R² 0.617
Residual Std. Err. 0.394
Residual DOF 658

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	893.2	0.4120
q_deriv	0.05002	0.6101
dyear	-0.8872	0.4140
dyear2	0.0002214	0.4137
cos_2t	0.04029	0.0660
sin_2t	0.2489	< 0.0001

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	-0.3548	< 0.0001
sin_t	-0.479	< 0.0001
log_q3	-0.01267	0.5284
log_q2	-0.009822	0.8530
log_q	0.06616	0.2128

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Sevenmile | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Sevenmile | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

• Observed
• Predicted

Term tribs_7mile_dike
Parameter TN
Samples 624
R² 0.371
Residual Std. Err. 0.503
Residual DOF 613

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	-4055	0.0052
q_deriv	0.009974	0.6834
dyear	4.057	0.0051
dyear2	-0.001013	0.0050
cos_2t	0.07004	0.0151
sin_2t	0.1325	< 0.0001

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	-0.4958	< 0.0001
sin_t	0.09251	0.0022
log_q3	0.009989	< 0.0001
log_q2	0.1589	< 0.0001
log_q	0.6447	< 0.0001

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Wood@Weed | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Wood@Weed | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

• Observed
• Predicted

Term tribs_wood_weed
Parameter TN
Samples 735
R² 0.186
Residual Std. Err. 0.331
Residual DOF 724

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	-435.7	0.6320
q_deriv	0.818	0.0001
dyear	0.4524	0.6182
dyear2	-0.000116	0.6083
cos_2t	0.02297	0.2057
sin_2t	0.03742	0.0355

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	-0.02743	0.2654
sin_t	0.04271	0.0224
log_q3	0.1866	0.0074
log_q2	0.831	< 0.0001
log_q	0.8374	< 0.0001

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Wood@Dike | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Wood@Dike | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

• Observed
• Predicted

Term tribs_wood_dike
Parameter TN
Samples 713
R² 0.206
Residual Std. Err. 0.458
Residual DOF 702

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	151.2	0.9039
q_deriv	0.2341	0.4217
dyear	-0.1238	0.9210
dyear2	2.539e-05	0.9350
cos_2t	0.01485	0.5549
sin_2t	0.04236	0.0868

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	-0.1292	< 0.0001
sin_t	0.1461	< 0.0001
log_q3	0.1164	0.0138
log_q2	0.5326	0.0003
log_q	0.5387	< 0.0001

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Sprague | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Sprague | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

• Observed
• Predicted

Term tribs_sprague
Parameter TN
Samples 621
R² 0.465
Residual Std. Err. 0.363
Residual DOF 610

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	-1636	0.1386
q_deriv	-0.01669	0.9305
dyear	1.639	0.1367
dyear2	-0.0004094	0.1361
cos_2t	0.01972	0.3515
sin_2t	0.1598	< 0.0001

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	-0.1562	< 0.0001
sin_t	0.02962	0.3437
log_q3	-0.1312	< 0.0001
log_q2	0.2322	< 0.0001
log_q	0.4293	< 0.0001

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Williamson | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Williamson | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

• Observed
• Predicted

Term tribs_williamson
Parameter TN
Samples 617
R² 0.731
Residual Std. Err. 0.31
Residual DOF 606

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	-3595	0.0002
q_deriv	-0.6437	0.0109
dyear	3.601	0.0002
dyear2	-0.0009004	0.0002
cos_2t	-0.01286	0.4866
sin_2t	0.1206	< 0.0001

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	-0.1239	< 0.0001
sin_t	0.1489	< 0.0001
log_q3	-0.2094	< 0.0001
log_q2	0.4456	0.0017
log_q	0.6171	< 0.0001

Estimated Daily Load and Concentration

Term: Lake Outflow | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

Regression Model Diagnostics

Term: Lake Outflow | Parameter: Total Nitrogen

• Observed
• Predicted

Term outflow
Parameter TN
Samples 667
R² 0.592
Residual Std. Err. 0.383
Residual DOF 656

	estimate	p.value
(Intercept)	-3325	0.0018
q_deriv	0.1333	0.1646
dyear	3.327	0.0018
dyear2	-0.0008301	0.0018
cos_2t	0.1948	< 0.0001
sin_2t	0.2474	< 0.0001

	estimate	p.value
cos_t	-0.008498	0.7936
sin_t	-0.4755	< 0.0001
log_q3	-0.019	0.3318
log_q2	0.0009564	0.9852
log_q	0.007206	0.8894

Figure C5: Comparison of regression-based and linear interpolation load estimation methods

Description: Comparison of predicted monthly and annual loads using primary load estimation method and simple linear interpolation of sampled concentrations

Methods:	Linear Interpolation	Daily loads computed by linearly interpolating sampled concentrations
	Residual Interpolation	Daily loads computed using estimated daily concentrations from interpolation of linear regression model residuals (primary method)

Panels:	A	Monthly loads estimated using each method by station
	B	Annual loads estimated using each method by station

Load Estimation Method Comparison

Parameter: Total Phosphorus

Load Estimation Method Comparison

Parameter: Total Nitrogen

Appendix D
Annual and Seasonal Variations in Mass Balance Terms

Table D1 Equations for computing flows and nutrient loads of derived mass balance terms

Figure D1 Annual and seasonal variations in flows, loads, and concentrations of mass balance terms

Table D1: Equations for computing flows and nutrient loads of derived mass balance terms

Term	Flows	Nutrient Loads
Wood@Dike - Wood@Weed	Computed by difference	same as flow
Williamson - Sprague	Computed by difference	same as flow
Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	Sevenmile@Dike + Wood@Dike + Williamson	same as flow
Total Pumped Inflows	ALR Pumped + WRDP Pumped + Ungauged Pumped	same as flow
Ungauged Inflows	Change in Storage + Lake Outflow + Evaporation - Total Gauged Trib. Inflows - Total Pumped Inflow - Precipitation	Flow * Ungauged Concentration
Total External Inflows	Total Gauged Trib. Inflows + Total Pumped Inflows + Ungauged Inflows	same as flow
Net Inflow	Total External Inflows + Precipitation - Evaporation	same as flow
Net Retention	Net Inflow - Lake Outflow - Change in Storage	same as flow
Background Sources	Total External Inflow	Flow * Background Concentration
Anthropogenic Sources	Total External Inflow	Total External Inflow Load - Background Sources Load

Figure D1: Annual and seasonal variations in flows, loads, and concentrations of mass balance terms

Description: Monthly and annual time series of flows, TP and TN loads, and concentrations for each mass balance term

Terms:

Label	Description
Sevenmile@Dike	Sevenmile Canal at Dike Road
Wood@Weed	Wood River at Weed Road
Wood@Dike - Wood@Weed	Wood River between Weed and Dike Roads
Wood@Dike	Wood River at Dike Road
Sprague	Sprague River
Williamson - Sprague	Williamson River excluding Sprague
Williamson	Williamson River
Total Gauged Trib. Inflows	Sevenmile@Dike + Wood@Dike + Williamson
ALR Pumped	Pumping from Agency Lake Ranch
WRDP Pumped	Pumping from Williamson River Delta Preserve
Ungauged Pumped	Pumping from other agricultural areas
Total Pumped Inflows	Total Pumping from ALR, WRDP, Ungauged Areas
Ungauged Inflows	Runoff and groundwater seepage from ungauged drainage areas
Total External Inflows	Total inflows from outside of the lake boundary (Gauged Tribs, Pumped, Ungauged)
Precipitation	
Evaporation	
Net Inflow	Total External Inflows + Precipitation - Evaporation
Lake Outflow	
Net Retention	Net Inflow - Lake Outflow - Change in Storage
Lake Mean Storage	
Anthropogenic Sources	
Background Sources	

Panels:

A	Timeseries of monthly flow, TP load, TP FWM concentration, TN load, TN FWM concentration
B	Seasonal variations in monthly flow, TP load, TP FWM concentration, TN load, TN FWM concentration Gray lines = monthly values for each water year Colored lines = long-term median for each month
C	Timeseries of monthly geomean and samples concentrations grouped by month

Term: Sevenmile

Date

Oct 1991 Oct 1993 Oct 1995 Oct 1997 Oct 1999 Oct 2001 Oct 2003 Oct 2005 Oct 2007 Oct 2009 Oct 2011 Oct 2013 Oct 2015 Oct 2017

Month

Oct Nov Dec Jan Feb Mar Apr May Jun Jul Aug Sep

Water Year

1992 1994 1996 1998 2000 2002 2004 2006 2008 2010 2012 2014 2016 2018

Term: Wood@Weed

Term: Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed

Term: Wood@Dike

Term: Sprague

Term: Williamson – Sprague

Term: Williamson

Oct 1991 Oct 1993 Oct 1995 Oct 1997 Oct 1999 Oct 2001 Oct 2003 Oct 2005 Oct 2007 Oct 2009 Oct 2011 Oct 2013 Oct 2015 Oct 2017

Date

Oct Nov Dec Jan Feb Mar Apr May Jun Jul Aug Sep

Month

1992 1994 1996 1998 2000 2002 2004 2006 2008 2010 2012 2014 2016 2018

Water Year

Term: Total Gauged Trib. Inflows

Term: ALR Pumped

Term: WRDP Pumped

Term: Ungauged Pumped

Term: Total Pumped Inflows

Term: Ungauged Inflows

Term: Total External Inflows

Term: Precipitation

Note: TP and TN loads include both dry and wet atmospheric deposition, concentrations computed by dividing total atmospheric deposition load by flow

Term: Evaporation

Oct 1991 Oct 1993 Oct 1995 Oct 1997 Oct 1999 Oct 2001 Oct 2003 Oct 2005 Oct 2007 Oct 2009 Oct 2011 Oct 2013 Oct 2015 Oct 2017

Date

Oct Nov Dec Jan Feb Mar Apr May Jun Jul Aug Sep

Month

1992 1994 1996 1998 2000 2002 2004 2006 2008 2010 2012 2014 2016 2018

Water Year

Term: Net Inflow

Term: Lake Outflow

Term: Net Retention

Term: Lake Mean Storage

Term: Background Inflows

Term: Anthropogenic Inflows

Appendix E

Water and Nutrient Mass Balance Summaries

Figure E1 Monthly flows, loads, and concentrations for gauged tributary inflow terms

Figure E2 Monthly flows, loads, and concentrations for major inflow terms

Figure E3 Monthly flows, loads, and concentrations for major lake budget terms

Figure E4 Multi-year aggregate flows, loads, and concentrations for gauged tributary inflow terms

Figure E5 Multi-year aggregate flows, loads, and concentrations for gauged tributary inflow terms as percent of total

Figure E6 Multi-year aggregate flows, loads, and concentrations for major inflow terms

Figure E7 Multi-year aggregate flows, loads, and concentrations for major inflow terms as percent of total

Figure E8 Multi-year aggregate flows, loads, and concentrations for major lake budget terms

Table E1 Annual mass balance summary tables

Table E2 Multi-year mass balance summary tables

Figure E1: Monthly flows, loads, and concentrations for gauged tributary inflow terms

Figure E2: Monthly flows, loads, and concentrations for major inflow terms

Figure E3: Monthly flows, loads, and concentrations for major lake budget terms

Note: Flows and loads for net retention and outflow are shown using reversed signs (multiply by -1) so that positive values denote additions to the water column and negative values indicate losses from the water column.

Figure E4: Multi-year aggregate flows, loads, and concentrations for gauged tributary inflow terms

Figure E5: Multi-year aggregate flows, loads, and concentrations for gauged tributary inflow terms as percent of total

Figure E6: Multi-year aggregate flows, loads, and concentrations for major inflow terms

Figure E7: Multi-year aggregate flows, loads, and concentrations for major inflow terms as percent of total

Figure E8: Multi-year aggregate flows, loads, and concentrations for major lake budget terms

Note: Flows and loads for net retention and outflow are shown using inverted values (multiply by -1) so that positive values denote additions to the water column and negative values indicate losses from the water column.

Table E1: Annual mass balance summary tables

Description: Annual mass balance summaries by water year, WY 1992–2018

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1992

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	81.6	11.0	39.4	9%	10%	13%	134	483	96	0.85	115	412
Wood River above Weed Road	167.9	14.9	28.0	18%	14%	10%	89	167	333	0.50	45	84
Wood River below Weed Road	42.0	9.3	22.5	4%	8%	8%	222	536	61	0.69	153	371
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	203.4	24.2	46.4	22%	22%	16%	119	228	394	0.52	61	118
Sprague River	178.0	12.8	47.1	19%	12%	16%	72	265	4,171	0.04	3	11
Williamson River excluding Sprague	254.6	32.0	29.9	27%	29%	10%	126	118	3,702	0.07	9	8
Total Williamson River	432.6	44.8	76.2	46%	41%	26%	104	176	7,873	0.05	6	10

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	717.6	79.9	162.0	76%	72%	55%	111	226	8,362	0.09	10	19
Total Pumped Area Inflows	47.1	19.1	115.8	5%	17%	39%	406	2,459	107	0.44	179	1,085
Ungauged Inflows	173.5	11.3	17.2	18%	10%	6%	65	99	1,034	0.17	11	17
Total External Inflows	938.1	110.3	294.9	100%	100%	100%	118	314	9,503	0.10	12	31
Precipitation	73.5	7.3	50.6	8%	7%	17%	100	688	269	0.27	27	188
Evaporation	278.2			30%					269	1.03		
Net Inflow	733.5	117.6	345.5	78%	107%	117%	160	471	9,772	0.08	12	35
Lake Outflow	796.8	127.1	1,716.5	85%	115%	582%	159	2,154	9,772	0.08	13	176
Storage Increase	-65.7	-75.6	-759.2	-7%	-69%	-257%						
Net Retention	2.3	66.2	-611.8	0%	60%	-207%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	938.1	61.0	92.9	100%	55%	31%	65	99	9,503	0.10	6	10
Anthropogenic		49.3	202.1		45%	69%	53	215	9,503		5	21

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	618.0	432.8	797.0
Area (km ²)	269.2	265.2	272.6
Elevation (ft)	4,139.7	4,137.4	4,141.8
Mean Depth (meters)	2.3	1.6	2.9

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.84 years
Net Water Load	3.49 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.41 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	60.0 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1993

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	84.1	14.3	43.3	5%	7%	6%	171	514	96	0.88	150	453
Wood River above Weed Road	211.1	21.8	32.0	12%	11%	4%	103	152	333	0.63	65	96
Wood River below Weed Road	57.6	20.5	60.8	3%	10%	8%	356	1,057	61	0.95	337	1,001
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	268.6	42.2	92.9	15%	21%	13%	157	346	394	0.68	107	236
Sprague River	703.5	68.7	354.0	39%	34%	48%	98	503	4,171	0.17	16	85
Williamson River excluding Sprague	300.2	33.9	105.8	17%	17%	14%	113	352	3,702	0.08	9	29
Total Williamson River	1,003.7	101.1	445.7	56%	50%	60%	101	444	7,873	0.13	13	57

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,356.5	157.6	581.9	76%	78%	79%	116	429	8,362	0.16	19	70
Total Pumped Area Inflows	48.5	19.7	119.2	3%	10%	16%	406	2,459	107	0.45	184	1,117
Ungauged Inflows	381.7	24.8	37.8	21%	12%	5%	65	99	1,033	0.37	24	37
Total External Inflows	1,786.6	202.1	738.8	100%	100%	100%	113	414	9,502	0.19	21	78
Precipitation	181.2	11.5	79.7	10%	6%	11%	64	440	270	0.67	43	295
Evaporation	251.9			14%					270	0.93		
Net Inflow	1,716.0	213.7	818.5	96%	106%	111%	125	477	9,772	0.18	22	84
Lake Outflow	1,545.3	134.8	2,175.3	86%	67%	294%	87	1,408	9,772	0.16	14	223
Storage Increase	170.7	-1.2	195.4	10%	-1%	26%						
Net Retention	0.0	80.0	-1,552.2	0%	40%	-210%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,786.6	116.1	176.9	100%	57%	24%	65	99	9,502	0.19	12	19
Anthropogenic		86.0	562.0		43%	76%	48	315	9,502		9	59

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	699.4	430.3	925.9
Area (km ²)	270.5	265.2	273.3
Elevation (ft)	4,140.6	4,137.4	4,143.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.6	1.6	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.41 years
Net Water Load	6.61 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.75 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	39.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1994

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	69.7	8.5	25.7	7%	8%	9%	122	369	96	0.73	89	269
Wood River above Weed Road	208.5	19.5	27.5	20%	18%	10%	93	132	333	0.63	59	83
Wood River below Weed Road	16.8	4.7	6.4	2%	4%	2%	283	383	61	0.28	78	106
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	186.6	22.0	31.5	18%	20%	11%	118	169	394	0.47	56	80
Sprague River	228.5	15.7	51.3	22%	14%	18%	69	224	4,171	0.05	4	12
Williamson River excluding Sprague	245.3	26.3	34.8	24%	24%	12%	107	142	3,702	0.07	7	9
Total Williamson River	473.7	42.0	85.7	46%	39%	30%	89	181	7,873	0.06	5	11

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	730.0	72.5	142.9	71%	67%	50%	99	196	8,362	0.09	9	17
Total Pumped Area Inflows	49.4	20.1	121.5	5%	19%	42%	406	2,459	107	0.46	188	1,139
Ungauged Inflows	242.0	15.7	24.0	24%	15%	8%	65	99	1,033	0.23	15	23
Total External Inflows	1,021.4	108.3	288.4	100%	100%	100%	106	282	9,502	0.11	11	30
Precipitation	71.1	7.2	49.9	7%	7%	17%	102	703	270	0.26	27	185
Evaporation	280.2			27%					270	1.04		
Net Inflow	812.3	115.5	338.3	80%	107%	117%	142	417	9,772	0.08	12	35
Lake Outflow	1,023.2	97.9	1,409.5	100%	90%	489%	96	1,378	9,772	0.10	10	144
Storage Increase	-215.1	-1.6	-245.7	-21%	-1%	-85%						
Net Retention	4.1	19.3	-825.5	0%	18%	-286%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,021.4	66.4	101.1	100%	61%	35%	65	99	9,502	0.11	7	11
Anthropogenic		41.9	187.2		39%	65%	41	183	9,502		4	20

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	666.4	387.6	835.2
Area (km ²)	270.2	262.9	272.9
Elevation (ft)	4,140.2	4,136.8	4,142.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.5	3.1

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.82 years
Net Water Load	3.78 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.40 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	17.8 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1995

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	86.8	10.9	45.0	5%	7%	7%	126	519	96	0.91	114	471
Wood River above Weed Road	195.8	16.2	34.3	12%	10%	5%	83	175	333	0.59	49	103
Wood River below Weed Road	51.8	17.4	35.2	3%	11%	5%	335	680	61	0.85	286	580
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	239.4	33.2	64.6	15%	20%	10%	139	270	394	0.61	84	164
Sprague River	647.1	51.4	287.8	40%	32%	44%	79	445	4,171	0.16	12	69
Williamson River excluding Sprague	271.1	29.3	112.5	17%	18%	17%	108	415	3,702	0.07	8	30
Total Williamson River	918.0	79.0	396.0	57%	49%	61%	86	431	7,873	0.12	10	50

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,244.3	123.2	505.6	78%	76%	77%	99	406	8,362	0.15	15	60
Total Pumped Area Inflows	48.2	19.5	118.4	3%	12%	18%	406	2,459	107	0.45	183	1,110
Ungauged Inflows	305.6	19.9	30.3	19%	12%	5%	65	99	1,033	0.30	19	29
Total External Inflows	1,598.0	162.6	654.3	100%	100%	100%	102	409	9,502	0.17	17	69
Precipitation	154.3	10.5	72.4	10%	6%	11%	68	469	270	0.57	39	268
Evaporation	255.7			16%					270	0.95		
Net Inflow	1,496.7	173.1	726.7	94%	106%	111%	116	486	9,772	0.15	18	74
Lake Outflow	1,262.7	139.4	2,043.5	79%	86%	312%	110	1,618	9,772	0.13	14	209
Storage Increase	234.0	89.3	960.0	15%	55%	147%						
Net Retention	0.0	-55.6	-2,276.8	0%	-34%	-348%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,598.0	103.9	158.2	100%	64%	24%	65	99	9,502	0.17	11	17
Anthropogenic		58.7	496.1		36%	76%	37	310	9,502		6	52

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	709.7	385.2	918.4
Area (km ²)	270.3	262.7	273.2
Elevation (ft)	4,140.8	4,136.8	4,143.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.6	1.5	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.47 years
Net Water Load	5.91 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.60 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-34.2 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1996

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	156.2	29.4	84.4	7%	13%	11%	188	540	96	1.63	307	883
Wood River above Weed Road	295.3	23.2	51.2	14%	10%	6%	79	173	333	0.89	70	154
Wood River below Weed Road	51.0	17.1	62.3	2%	7%	8%	336	1,222	61	0.84	282	1,025
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	342.5	40.3	109.6	16%	17%	14%	118	320	394	0.87	102	278
Sprague River	826.2	65.7	335.0	39%	28%	42%	80	405	4,171	0.20	16	80
Williamson River excluding Sprague	326.6	49.1	110.8	15%	21%	14%	150	339	3,702	0.09	13	30
Total Williamson River	1,152.7	114.7	432.1	55%	49%	54%	99	375	7,873	0.15	15	55

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,651.4	184.4	626.1	78%	79%	78%	112	379	8,362	0.20	22	75
Total Pumped Area Inflows	53.8	21.8	132.3	3%	9%	17%	406	2,459	107	0.50	205	1,240
Ungauged Inflows	404.4	26.3	40.0	19%	11%	5%	65	99	1,031	0.39	25	39
Total External Inflows	2,109.7	232.5	798.4	100%	100%	100%	110	378	9,501	0.22	24	84
Precipitation	178.8	11.5	79.2	8%	5%	10%	64	443	271	0.66	42	292
Evaporation	251.9			12%					271	0.93		
Net Inflow	2,036.6	244.0	877.6	97%	105%	110%	120	431	9,772	0.21	25	90
Lake Outflow	2,098.8	182.8	3,037.6	99%	79%	380%	87	1,447	9,772	0.21	19	311
Storage Increase	-62.2	-37.8	-233.4	-3%	-16%	-29%						
Net Retention	0.0	99.0	-1,926.6	0%	43%	-241%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	2,109.7	137.1	208.9	100%	59%	26%	65	99	9,501	0.22	14	22
Anthropogenic		95.4	589.5		41%	74%	45	279	9,501		10	62

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	752.5	560.2	921.8
Area (km ²)	271.5	267.4	273.3
Elevation (ft)	4,141.3	4,139.0	4,143.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.8	2.1	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.37 years
Net Water Load	7.77 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.86 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	42.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1997

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	170.6	19.3	69.1	8%	9%	9%	113	405	96	1.78	202	723
Wood River above Weed Road	356.7	28.6	51.3	16%	13%	6%	80	144	333	1.07	86	154
Wood River below Weed Road	58.5	15.3	26.4	3%	7%	3%	262	452	61	0.96	252	435
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	408.1	44.0	77.7	19%	21%	10%	108	190	394	1.04	112	197
Sprague River	811.0	65.3	273.0	37%	31%	34%	81	337	4,171	0.19	16	65
Williamson River excluding Sprague	410.6	41.5	220.5	19%	19%	27%	101	537	3,702	0.11	11	60
Total Williamson River	1,221.6	106.3	493.5	56%	50%	61%	87	404	7,873	0.16	14	63

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,800.3	169.6	640.3	83%	80%	79%	94	356	8,362	0.22	20	77
Total Pumped Area Inflows	57.0	23.1	140.1	3%	11%	17%	406	2,459	107	0.53	217	1,313
Ungauged Inflows	312.9	20.3	31.0	14%	10%	4%	65	99	1,031	0.30	20	30
Total External Inflows	2,170.2	213.1	811.3	100%	100%	100%	98	374	9,500	0.23	22	85
Precipitation	167.6	11.0	76.1	8%	5%	9%	66	454	272	0.62	41	280
Evaporation	242.4			11%					272	0.89		
Net Inflow	2,095.5	224.1	887.5	97%	105%	109%	107	424	9,772	0.21	23	91
Lake Outflow	1,990.9	234.3	3,120.9	92%	110%	385%	118	1,568	9,772	0.20	24	319
Storage Increase	102.6	14.5	82.9	5%	7%	10%						
Net Retention	2.0	-24.7	-2,316.3	0%	-12%	-286%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	2,170.2	141.1	214.9	100%	66%	26%	65	99	9,500	0.23	15	23
Anthropogenic		72.0	596.5		34%	74%	33	275	9,500		8	63

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	759.3	539.9	906.0
Area (km ²)	271.6	267.1	273.2
Elevation (ft)	4,141.4	4,138.7	4,143.1
Mean Depth (meters)	2.8	2.0	3.3

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.36 years
Net Water Load	7.99 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.78 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-11.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1998

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	166.9	18.9	68.2	8%	9%	9%	113	409	96	1.75	197	714
Wood River above Weed Road	330.2	26.3	42.8	16%	13%	5%	80	130	333	0.99	79	128
Wood River below Weed Road	72.6	12.6	21.2	3%	6%	3%	173	293	61	1.19	207	349
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	402.0	38.9	63.8	19%	19%	8%	97	159	394	1.02	99	162
Sprague River	774.4	56.0	274.9	37%	27%	35%	72	355	4,171	0.19	13	66
Williamson River excluding Sprague	433.9	52.9	235.2	21%	26%	30%	122	542	3,702	0.12	14	64
Total Williamson River	1,208.3	108.8	510.2	57%	53%	64%	90	422	7,873	0.15	14	65

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,777.2	166.6	642.2	84%	81%	81%	94	361	8,362	0.21	20	77
Total Pumped Area Inflows	50.9	19.6	123.2	2%	10%	16%	386	2,423	103	0.49	190	1,192
Ungauged Inflows	282.1	18.3	27.9	13%	9%	4%	65	99	1,034	0.27	18	27
Total External Inflows	2,110.1	204.6	793.3	100%	100%	100%	97	376	9,500	0.22	22	84
Precipitation	139.6	9.9	68.7	7%	5%	9%	71	492	272	0.51	37	252
Evaporation	231.7			11%					272	0.85		
Net Inflow	2,018.0	214.6	862.0	96%	105%	109%	106	427	9,772	0.21	22	88
Lake Outflow	2,034.6	192.4	2,628.9	96%	94%	331%	95	1,292	9,772	0.21	20	269
Storage Increase	-17.3	-11.7	-264.0	-1%	-6%	-33%						
Net Retention	0.7	33.9	-1,502.9	0%	17%	-189%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	2,110.1	137.2	208.9	100%	67%	26%	65	99	9,500	0.22	14	22
Anthropogenic		67.5	584.4		33%	74%	32	277	9,500		7	62

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	792.3	645.5	911.0
Area (km ²)	272.3	270.4	273.2
Elevation (ft)	4,141.8	4,140.0	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.9	2.4	3.3

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.39 years
Net Water Load	7.75 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.75 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	16.5 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1999

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	143.4	20.8	59.4	6%	9%	8%	145	414	96	1.50	217	621
Wood River above Weed Road	242.0	21.2	28.3	10%	10%	4%	88	117	333	0.73	64	85
Wood River below Weed Road	112.3	20.5	31.6	5%	9%	4%	183	281	61	1.85	338	519
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	354.3	41.7	59.9	15%	19%	8%	118	169	394	0.90	106	152
Sprague River	807.5	65.5	256.5	35%	30%	35%	81	318	4,171	0.19	16	62
Williamson River excluding Sprague	478.4	42.9	180.9	21%	20%	25%	90	378	3,702	0.13	12	49
Total Williamson River	1,285.9	108.4	437.4	56%	49%	60%	84	340	7,873	0.16	14	56

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,783.6	170.9	556.7	77%	78%	77%	96	312	8,362	0.21	20	67
Total Pumped Area Inflows	51.3	17.8	120.6	2%	8%	17%	346	2,350	97	0.53	184	1,246
Ungauged Inflows	471.1	30.6	46.6	20%	14%	6%	65	99	1,041	0.45	29	45
Total External Inflows	2,306.0	219.3	723.9	100%	100%	100%	95	314	9,500	0.24	23	76
Precipitation	127.1	9.4	65.3	6%	4%	9%	74	514	272	0.47	35	240
Evaporation	255.2			11%					272	0.94		
Net Inflow	2,177.8	228.8	789.2	94%	104%	109%	105	362	9,772	0.22	23	81
Lake Outflow	2,152.3	255.0	3,211.8	93%	116%	444%	118	1,492	9,772	0.22	26	329
Storage Increase	25.5	6.1	79.2	1%	3%	11%						
Net Retention	0.0	-32.4	-2,501.8	0%	-15%	-346%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	2,306.0	149.9	228.3	100%	68%	32%	65	99	9,500	0.24	16	24
Anthropogenic		69.4	495.6		32%	68%	30	215	9,500		7	52

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	772.4	637.2	900.1
Area (km ²)	272.2	270.3	273.2
Elevation (ft)	4,141.5	4,139.9	4,143.1
Mean Depth (meters)	2.8	2.4	3.3

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.35 years
Net Water Load	8.47 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.81 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-14.8 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2000

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	90.5	9.6	34.1	5%	5%	5%	106	377	96	0.95	100	357
Wood River above Weed Road	252.4	20.2	32.2	14%	10%	5%	80	128	333	0.76	61	97
Wood River below Weed Road	101.4	14.8	28.5	5%	7%	4%	146	281	61	1.67	244	469
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	353.9	35.0	60.7	19%	18%	9%	99	172	394	0.90	89	154
Sprague River	508.8	34.6	153.7	27%	17%	23%	68	302	4,171	0.12	8	37
Williamson River excluding Sprague	470.9	39.0	176.3	25%	20%	27%	83	374	3,702	0.13	11	48
Total Williamson River	979.7	73.5	329.9	53%	37%	50%	75	337	7,873	0.12	9	42

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,424.0	118.1	424.8	77%	60%	64%	83	298	8,362	0.17	14	51
Total Pumped Area Inflows	51.2	55.1	198.0	3%	28%	30%	1,076	3,868	90	0.57	611	2,197
Ungauged Inflows	384.9	25.0	38.1	21%	13%	6%	65	99	1,048	0.37	24	36
Total External Inflows	1,860.2	198.2	660.9	100%	100%	100%	107	355	9,500	0.20	21	70
Precipitation	101.9	8.5	58.5	5%	4%	9%	83	574	272	0.37	31	215
Evaporation	247.8			13%					272	0.91		
Net Inflow	1,714.3	206.7	719.5	92%	104%	109%	121	420	9,772	0.18	21	74
Lake Outflow	1,775.2	220.9	2,391.6	95%	111%	362%	124	1,347	9,772	0.18	23	245
Storage Increase	-60.9	0.9	143.4	-3%	0%	22%						
Net Retention	0.0	-15.1	-1,815.5	0%	-8%	-275%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,860.2	120.9	184.2	100%	61%	28%	65	99	9,500	0.20	13	19
Anthropogenic		77.3	476.8		39%	72%	42	256	9,500		8	50

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	768.2	589.6	930.9
Area (km ²)	271.9	268.0	273.3
Elevation (ft)	4,141.5	4,139.3	4,143.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.8	2.2	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.45 years
Net Water Load	6.84 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.73 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-7.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2001

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	58.5	6.9	20.0	5%	6%	6%	118	341	96	0.61	72	209
Wood River above Weed Road	200.7	16.4	24.5	16%	15%	8%	82	122	333	0.60	49	74
Wood River below Weed Road	74.4	12.3	16.2	6%	11%	5%	165	218	61	1.22	202	267
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	275.1	28.7	40.8	22%	26%	13%	104	148	394	0.70	73	103
Sprague River	259.5	15.5	59.4	21%	14%	19%	60	229	4,171	0.06	4	14
Williamson River excluding Sprague	362.9	32.1	105.8	29%	29%	33%	88	291	3,702	0.10	9	29
Total Williamson River	622.4	47.7	163.4	50%	43%	52%	77	263	7,873	0.08	6	21

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	956.0	83.3	224.1	77%	76%	71%	87	234	8,362	0.11	10	27
Total Pumped Area Inflows	20.8	9.1	65.2	2%	8%	21%	439	3,138	87	0.24	105	751
Ungauged Inflows	267.9	17.4	26.5	22%	16%	8%	65	99	1,051	0.25	17	25
Total External Inflows	1,244.7	109.8	315.9	100%	100%	100%	88	254	9,500	0.13	12	33
Precipitation	60.6	6.8	47.3	5%	6%	15%	113	780	272	0.22	25	174
Evaporation	296.9			24%					272	1.09		
Net Inflow	1,008.3	116.6	363.2	81%	106%	115%	116	360	9,772	0.10	12	37
Lake Outflow	1,006.7	129.8	2,178.1	81%	118%	690%	129	2,164	9,772	0.10	13	223
Storage Increase	1.6	-27.9	443.6	0%	-25%	140%						
Net Retention	0.0	14.8	-2,258.6	0%	13%	-715%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,244.7	80.9	123.2	100%	74%	39%	65	99	9,500	0.13	9	13
Anthropogenic		28.9	192.6		26%	61%	23	155	9,500		3	20

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	747.2	603.5	906.8
Area (km ²)	271.7	269.4	273.2
Elevation (ft)	4,141.2	4,139.5	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.8	2.2	3.3

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.74 years
Net Water Load	4.58 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.40 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	13.5 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2002

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	49.8	9.0	25.6	4%	6%	5%	180	514	96	0.52	94	268
Wood River above Weed Road	202.4	17.9	24.1	15%	12%	5%	89	119	333	0.61	54	72
Wood River below Weed Road	75.8	12.7	18.2	5%	8%	4%	167	240	61	1.25	209	299
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	277.7	30.6	42.2	20%	20%	9%	110	152	394	0.70	78	107
Sprague River	354.8	24.8	119.8	26%	16%	25%	70	338	4,171	0.09	6	29
Williamson River excluding Sprague	360.4	37.0	147.4	26%	24%	31%	103	409	3,702	0.10	10	40
Total Williamson River	715.2	61.8	267.1	52%	41%	55%	86	374	7,873	0.09	8	34

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,042.6	101.4	334.9	75%	67%	70%	97	321	8,362	0.12	12	40
Total Pumped Area Inflows	39.8	30.3	116.8	3%	20%	24%	761	2,931	87	0.46	349	1,344
Ungauged Inflows	301.7	19.6	29.9	22%	13%	6%	65	99	1,051	0.29	19	28
Total External Inflows	1,384.2	151.3	481.5	100%	100%	100%	109	348	9,501	0.15	16	51
Precipitation	104.8	8.6	59.2	8%	6%	12%	82	565	271	0.39	32	218
Evaporation	268.3			19%					271	0.99		
Net Inflow	1,220.6	159.9	540.7	88%	106%	112%	131	443	9,772	0.12	16	55
Lake Outflow	1,303.1	113.6	2,236.7	94%	75%	464%	87	1,716	9,772	0.13	12	229
Storage Increase	-82.4	28.7	-380.9	-6%	19%	-79%						
Net Retention	0.0	17.6	-1,315.1	0%	12%	-273%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,384.2	90.0	137.0	100%	59%	28%	65	99	9,501	0.15	9	14
Anthropogenic		61.3	344.5		41%	72%	44	249	9,501		6	36

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	740.3	529.3	908.5
Area (km ²)	271.4	266.9	273.2
Elevation (ft)	4,141.1	4,138.6	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.7	2.0	3.3

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.61 years
Net Water Load	5.10 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.56 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	11.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2003

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	120.8	16.3	56.4	9%	11%	11%	135	467	96	1.26	170	590
Wood River above Weed Road	202.7	17.4	25.1	15%	12%	5%	86	124	333	0.61	52	75
Wood River below Weed Road	125.7	15.4	23.1	9%	11%	4%	123	184	61	2.07	254	380
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	328.4	32.8	47.7	24%	23%	9%	100	145	394	0.83	83	121
Sprague River	394.8	26.2	102.8	29%	18%	19%	66	260	4,171	0.09	6	25
Williamson River excluding Sprague	319.6	30.8	190.5	23%	22%	36%	96	596	3,702	0.09	8	51
Total Williamson River	714.4	57.0	293.3	52%	40%	55%	80	410	7,873	0.09	7	37

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,163.6	106.1	397.3	84%	74%	75%	91	341	8,362	0.14	13	48
Total Pumped Area Inflows	43.1	25.3	118.4	3%	18%	22%	587	2,751	87	0.50	291	1,364
Ungauged Inflows	172.1	11.2	17.0	12%	8%	3%	65	99	1,052	0.16	11	16
Total External Inflows	1,378.7	142.5	532.8	100%	100%	100%	103	386	9,501	0.15	15	56
Precipitation	115.6	9.0	62.0	8%	6%	12%	78	537	271	0.43	33	229
Evaporation	268.9			20%					271	0.99		
Net Inflow	1,225.4	151.5	594.8	89%	106%	112%	124	485	9,772	0.13	16	61
Lake Outflow	1,154.0	142.4	2,127.9	84%	100%	399%	123	1,844	9,772	0.12	15	218
Storage Increase	35.8	19.0	201.8	3%	13%	38%						
Net Retention	35.6	-9.9	-1,734.9	3%	-7%	-326%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,378.7	89.6	136.5	100%	63%	26%	65	99	9,501	0.15	9	14
Anthropogenic		52.9	396.3		37%	74%	38	287	9,501		6	42

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	730.1	522.8	918.4
Area (km ²)	270.9	266.8	273.2
Elevation (ft)	4,141.0	4,138.5	4,143.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.7	2.0	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.60 years
Net Water Load	5.09 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.53 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-6.9 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2004

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	89.2	11.9	47.3	7%	9%	11%	134	530	96	0.93	125	494
Wood River above Weed Road	207.4	17.8	27.0	15%	14%	6%	86	130	333	0.62	53	81
Wood River below Weed Road	109.5	16.2	24.4	8%	12%	6%	148	223	61	1.80	267	401
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	317.0	34.0	51.4	24%	26%	12%	107	162	394	0.80	86	130
Sprague River	342.8	24.6	128.7	25%	19%	30%	72	375	4,171	0.08	6	31
Williamson River excluding Sprague	303.2	30.0	92.7	23%	23%	21%	99	306	3,702	0.08	8	25
Total Williamson River	646.1	54.5	220.9	48%	42%	51%	84	342	7,873	0.08	7	28

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,052.2	100.5	319.6	78%	77%	73%	96	304	8,362	0.13	12	38
Total Pumped Area Inflows	30.9	12.9	89.4	2%	10%	21%	416	2,890	87	0.36	148	1,030
Ungauged Inflows	261.4	17.0	25.9	19%	13%	6%	65	99	1,052	0.25	16	25
Total External Inflows	1,344.6	130.4	434.8	100%	100%	100%	97	323	9,502	0.14	14	46
Precipitation	103.7	8.5	58.9	8%	7%	14%	82	567	270	0.38	32	218
Evaporation	264.3			20%					270	0.98		
Net Inflow	1,183.9	138.9	493.7	88%	107%	114%	117	417	9,772	0.12	14	51
Lake Outflow	1,191.3	117.1	2,116.6	89%	90%	487%	98	1,777	9,772	0.12	12	217
Storage Increase	-7.3	-66.4	-433.6	-1%	-51%	-100%						
Net Retention	0.0	88.2	-1,189.3	0%	68%	-274%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,344.6	87.4	133.1	100%	67%	31%	65	99	9,502	0.14	9	14
Anthropogenic		43.0	301.7		33%	69%	32	224	9,502		5	32

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	696.2	536.6	875.1
Area (km ²)	270.5	267.0	273.0
Elevation (ft)	4,140.6	4,138.7	4,142.8
Mean Depth (meters)	2.6	2.0	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.59 years
Net Water Load	4.97 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.48 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	67.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2005

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	81.0	10.3	41.3	6%	8%	9%	127	510	96	0.85	107	432
Wood River above Weed Road	206.9	17.2	26.1	17%	13%	5%	83	126	333	0.62	52	78
Wood River below Weed Road	101.0	15.7	28.1	8%	12%	6%	155	278	61	1.66	258	462
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	307.8	32.8	54.1	25%	25%	11%	107	176	394	0.78	83	137
Sprague River	383.9	31.9	152.3	31%	24%	32%	83	397	4,171	0.09	8	37
Williamson River excluding Sprague	263.8	28.5	64.2	21%	21%	13%	108	243	3,702	0.07	8	17
Total Williamson River	647.7	60.3	216.3	52%	45%	45%	93	334	7,873	0.08	8	27

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,036.5	103.4	311.7	83%	77%	65%	100	301	8,362	0.12	12	37
Total Pumped Area Inflows	49.0	19.4	153.0	4%	15%	32%	397	3,124	87	0.56	224	1,762
Ungauged Inflows	168.2	10.9	16.7	13%	8%	3%	65	99	1,051	0.16	10	16
Total External Inflows	1,253.7	133.8	481.3	100%	100%	100%	107	384	9,500	0.13	14	51
Precipitation	82.4	7.7	53.1	7%	6%	11%	93	645	272	0.30	28	196
Evaporation	242.5			19%					272	0.89		
Net Inflow	1,093.6	141.5	534.5	87%	106%	111%	129	489	9,772	0.11	14	55
Lake Outflow	1,052.9	118.3	1,953.9	84%	88%	406%	112	1,856	9,772	0.11	12	200
Storage Increase	20.4	21.4	176.8	2%	16%	37%						
Net Retention	20.3	1.8	-1,596.2	2%	1%	-332%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,253.7	81.5	124.1	100%	61%	26%	65	99	9,500	0.13	9	13
Anthropogenic		52.3	357.2		39%	74%	42	285	9,500		6	38

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	757.5	549.6	912.6
Area (km ²)	271.5	267.2	273.2
Elevation (ft)	4,141.4	4,138.8	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.8	2.1	3.3

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.69 years
Net Water Load	4.62 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.49 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	1.3 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2006

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	132.7	25.0	88.2	6%	11%	10%	188	665	96	1.39	261	923
Wood River above Weed Road	250.3	22.6	39.3	11%	10%	4%	90	157	333	0.75	68	118
Wood River below Weed Road	93.1	21.2	43.6	4%	9%	5%	228	469	61	1.53	349	718
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	343.4	43.8	83.0	15%	19%	9%	128	242	394	0.87	111	211
Sprague River	864.8	74.8	328.6	39%	32%	37%	86	380	4,171	0.21	18	79
Williamson River excluding Sprague	381.0	42.4	233.5	17%	18%	26%	111	613	3,702	0.10	11	63
Total Williamson River	1,245.4	117.1	550.1	56%	50%	62%	94	442	7,873	0.16	15	70

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,721.5	185.9	721.3	77%	79%	81%	108	419	8,362	0.21	22	86
Total Pumped Area Inflows	40.7	19.9	120.6	2%	8%	14%	488	2,965	85	0.48	234	1,421
Ungauged Inflows	469.9	30.5	46.5	21%	13%	5%	65	99	1,051	0.45	29	44
Total External Inflows	2,232.0	236.3	888.4	100%	100%	100%	106	398	9,499	0.23	25	94
Precipitation	154.5	10.5	72.8	7%	4%	8%	68	471	273	0.56	39	266
Evaporation	259.2			12%					273	0.95		
Net Inflow	2,127.3	246.8	961.2	95%	104%	108%	116	452	9,772	0.22	25	98
Lake Outflow	2,159.9	214.4	3,288.9	97%	91%	370%	99	1,523	9,772	0.22	22	337
Storage Increase	-32.6	59.7	328.0	-1%	25%	37%						
Net Retention	0.0	-27.2	-2,655.7	0%	-12%	-299%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	2,232.0	145.1	221.0	100%	61%	25%	65	99	9,499	0.23	15	23
Anthropogenic		91.2	667.4		39%	75%	41	299	9,499		10	70

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	747.7	545.6	918.4
Area (km ²)	273.5	267.4	282.2
Elevation (ft)	4,141.2	4,138.7	4,143.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.7	2.0	3.3

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.35 years
Net Water Load	8.16 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.86 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-11.5 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2007

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	104.2	18.9	54.9	7%	12%	11%	181	527	96	1.09	197	574
Wood River above Weed Road	257.4	20.9	34.0	17%	14%	7%	81	132	333	0.77	63	102
Wood River below Weed Road	111.3	21.5	36.9	7%	14%	8%	193	332	61	1.83	354	607
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	368.7	42.4	70.5	24%	28%	14%	115	191	394	0.94	108	179
Sprague River	395.9	25.6	118.7	26%	17%	24%	65	300	4,171	0.09	6	28
Williamson River excluding Sprague	327.9	31.4	95.0	22%	21%	19%	96	290	3,702	0.09	8	26
Total Williamson River	723.9	57.0	213.7	48%	37%	44%	79	295	7,873	0.09	7	27

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,196.7	118.3	339.1	79%	78%	69%	99	283	8,362	0.14	14	41
Total Pumped Area Inflows	40.5	16.0	123.0	3%	11%	25%	396	3,041	78	0.52	205	1,573
Ungauged Inflows	278.4	18.1	27.6	18%	12%	6%	65	99	1,051	0.26	17	26
Total External Inflows	1,515.6	152.4	489.7	100%	100%	100%	101	323	9,492	0.16	16	52
Precipitation	104.2	8.7	60.0	7%	6%	12%	83	576	280	0.37	31	214
Evaporation	268.4			18%					280	0.96		
Net Inflow	1,351.4	161.1	549.7	89%	106%	112%	119	407	9,772	0.14	16	56
Lake Outflow	1,388.5	244.3	2,969.1	92%	160%	606%	176	2,138	9,772	0.14	25	304
Storage Increase	-37.0	-44.7	-307.9	-2%	-29%	-63%						
Net Retention	0.0	-38.6	-2,111.5	0%	-25%	-431%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,515.6	98.5	150.0	100%	65%	31%	65	99	9,492	0.16	10	16
Anthropogenic		53.9	339.6		35%	69%	36	224	9,492		6	36

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	730.0	508.5	939.3
Area (km ²)	280.3	275.6	283.3
Elevation (ft)	4,140.9	4,138.3	4,143.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.6	1.8	3.3

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.54 years
Net Water Load	5.41 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.54 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-25.3 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2008

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	92.5	13.3	41.8	6%	9%	8%	143	451	96	0.97	139	437
Wood River above Weed Road	250.8	22.2	29.8	16%	15%	6%	88	119	333	0.75	66	90
Wood River below Weed Road	109.8	16.8	30.2	7%	11%	6%	153	275	61	1.81	275	496
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	360.6	38.9	59.8	23%	27%	12%	108	166	394	0.92	99	152
Sprague River	455.4	32.1	165.7	30%	22%	32%	71	364	4,171	0.11	8	40
Williamson River excluding Sprague	339.7	33.0	101.4	22%	23%	20%	97	298	3,702	0.09	9	27
Total Williamson River	795.1	65.1	267.1	52%	45%	52%	82	336	7,873	0.10	8	34

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,248.2	117.2	368.6	81%	80%	71%	94	295	8,362	0.15	14	44
Total Pumped Area Inflows	49.7	12.9	125.6	3%	9%	24%	261	2,529	87	0.57	149	1,446
Ungauged Inflows	244.0	15.9	24.2	16%	11%	5%	65	99	1,041	0.23	15	23
Total External Inflows	1,541.9	146.0	518.4	100%	100%	100%	95	336	9,490	0.16	15	55
Precipitation	103.7	8.7	60.2	7%	6%	12%	84	580	282	0.37	31	213
Evaporation	271.5			18%					282	0.96		
Net Inflow	1,374.2	154.7	578.6	89%	106%	112%	113	421	9,772	0.14	16	59
Lake Outflow	1,323.7	173.5	2,824.3	86%	119%	545%	131	2,134	9,772	0.14	18	289
Storage Increase	50.5	20.5	118.3	3%	14%	23%						
Net Retention	0.0	-39.3	-2,364.1	0%	-27%	-456%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,541.9	100.2	152.6	100%	69%	29%	65	99	9,490	0.16	11	16
Anthropogenic		45.8	365.7		31%	71%	30	237	9,490		5	39

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	715.6	497.6	924.0
Area (km ²)	282.0	266.4	288.3
Elevation (ft)	4,140.6	4,138.2	4,143.0
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.9	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.52 years
Net Water Load	5.47 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.52 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-26.9 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2009

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	107.1	14.4	56.4	8%	12%	14%	134	526	96	1.12	150	590
Wood River above Weed Road	249.9	20.8	30.8	18%	17%	8%	83	123	333	0.75	62	93
Wood River below Weed Road	119.1	16.2	32.4	9%	13%	8%	136	272	61	1.96	267	533
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	369.0	37.0	63.2	26%	30%	16%	100	171	394	0.94	94	161
Sprague River	310.6	18.5	95.1	22%	15%	23%	60	306	4,171	0.07	4	23
Williamson River excluding Sprague	354.8	31.2	84.8	25%	26%	21%	88	239	3,702	0.10	8	23
Total Williamson River	665.4	49.7	179.7	48%	41%	44%	75	270	7,873	0.08	6	23

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,141.5	101.1	299.3	82%	83%	74%	89	262	8,362	0.14	12	36
Total Pumped Area Inflows	39.1	7.0	83.6	3%	6%	21%	179	2,135	87	0.45	81	962
Ungauged Inflows	218.9	14.2	21.7	16%	12%	5%	65	99	1,035	0.21	14	21
Total External Inflows	1,399.5	122.3	404.5	100%	100%	100%	87	289	9,484	0.15	13	43
Precipitation	111.8	9.1	62.9	8%	7%	16%	81	563	288	0.39	32	219
Evaporation	270.6			19%					288	0.94		
Net Inflow	1,240.6	131.4	467.4	89%	107%	116%	106	377	9,772	0.13	13	48
Lake Outflow	1,280.0	150.6	2,532.3	91%	123%	626%	118	1,978	9,772	0.13	15	259
Storage Increase	-53.0	-35.4	-227.2	-4%	-29%	-56%						
Net Retention	13.6	16.2	-1,837.7	1%	13%	-454%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,399.5	91.0	138.6	100%	74%	34%	65	99	9,484	0.15	10	15
Anthropogenic		31.4	266.0		26%	66%	22	190	9,484		3	28

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	714.1	506.0	911.6
Area (km ²)	287.8	277.2	296.0
Elevation (ft)	4,140.5	4,138.2	4,142.8
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.8	3.1

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.58 years
Net Water Load	4.86 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.43 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	13.2 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2010

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	108.4	14.0	45.1	9%	12%	15%	129	416	96	1.13	147	471
Wood River above Weed Road	234.8	20.5	26.2	19%	18%	9%	87	112	333	0.71	61	79
Wood River below Weed Road	85.7	12.3	22.7	7%	11%	8%	144	265	61	1.41	203	373
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	320.5	32.8	48.9	26%	29%	16%	102	153	394	0.81	83	124
Sprague River	283.3	17.8	75.5	23%	16%	25%	63	267	4,171	0.07	4	18
Williamson River excluding Sprague	325.0	31.6	57.5	26%	28%	19%	97	177	3,702	0.09	9	16
Total Williamson River	608.3	49.4	132.9	49%	44%	45%	81	219	7,873	0.08	6	17

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,037.2	96.2	226.9	83%	85%	76%	93	219	8,362	0.12	12	27
Total Pumped Area Inflows	18.1	5.1	53.1	1%	4%	18%	281	2,938	87	0.21	58	611
Ungauged Inflows	189.1	12.3	18.7	15%	11%	6%	65	99	1,038	0.18	12	18
Total External Inflows	1,244.4	113.6	298.7	100%	100%	100%	91	240	9,487	0.13	12	31
Precipitation	95.7	8.4	58.3	8%	7%	20%	88	609	285	0.34	30	204
Evaporation	264.2			21%					285	0.93		
Net Inflow	1,075.9	122.0	357.0	86%	107%	120%	113	332	9,772	0.11	12	37
Lake Outflow	1,014.8	96.2	1,685.4	82%	85%	564%	95	1,661	9,772	0.10	10	172
Storage Increase	61.1	15.3	107.4	5%	14%	36%						
Net Retention	0.0	10.5	-1,435.9	0%	9%	-481%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,244.4	80.9	123.2	100%	71%	41%	65	99	9,487	0.13	9	13
Anthropogenic		32.7	175.5		29%	59%	26	141	9,487		3	19

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	640.6	479.0	803.9
Area (km ²)	284.9	275.4	293.2
Elevation (ft)	4,139.7	4,137.8	4,141.6
Mean Depth (meters)	2.2	1.7	2.7

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.60 years
Net Water Load	4.37 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.40 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	9.2 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2011

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	117.4	15.2	60.7	7%	8%	10%	129	517	96	1.23	159	635
Wood River above Weed Road	260.2	23.6	29.7	15%	13%	5%	91	114	333	0.78	71	89
Wood River below Weed Road	87.5	16.6	32.0	5%	9%	5%	190	366	61	1.44	274	527
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	341.7	40.0	61.3	19%	22%	10%	117	179	394	0.87	102	156
Sprague River	679.6	52.4	268.7	38%	29%	43%	77	395	4,171	0.16	13	64
Williamson River excluding Sprague	309.8	35.9	67.0	17%	20%	11%	116	216	3,702	0.08	10	18
Total Williamson River	989.4	88.3	333.3	55%	48%	53%	89	337	7,873	0.13	11	42

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,448.6	143.5	455.3	81%	78%	73%	99	314	8,362	0.17	17	54
Total Pumped Area Inflows	45.2	20.9	142.5	3%	11%	23%	463	3,152	87	0.52	241	1,641
Ungauged Inflows	299.7	19.5	29.7	17%	11%	5%	65	99	1,032	0.29	19	29
Total External Inflows	1,793.5	183.9	627.5	100%	100%	100%	103	350	9,482	0.19	19	66
Precipitation	142.8	10.4	71.6	8%	6%	11%	73	501	290	0.49	36	246
Evaporation	258.1			14%					290	0.89		
Net Inflow	1,678.2	194.3	699.1	94%	106%	111%	116	417	9,772	0.17	20	72
Lake Outflow	1,653.4	135.9	1,925.6	92%	74%	307%	82	1,165	9,772	0.17	14	197
Storage Increase	24.8	-9.6	-402.8	1%	-5%	-64%						
Net Retention	0.0	68.0	-823.8	0%	37%	-131%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,793.5	116.6	177.6	100%	63%	28%	65	99	9,482	0.19	12	19
Anthropogenic		67.4	449.9		37%	72%	38	251	9,482		7	47

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	769.7	554.4	948.7
Area (km ²)	290.5	279.3	296.8
Elevation (ft)	4,141.2	4,138.7	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.6	2.0	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.46 years
Net Water Load	6.17 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.63 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	37.0 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2012

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	59.4	8.0	25.1	4%	6%	6%	135	422	96	0.62	84	262
Wood River above Weed Road	290.0	26.1	32.7	20%	19%	8%	90	113	333	0.87	78	98
Wood River below Weed Road	91.8	16.4	29.4	6%	12%	7%	179	320	61	1.51	270	484
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	381.8	42.5	62.1	26%	31%	14%	111	163	394	0.97	108	158
Sprague River	380.1	26.4	143.1	26%	19%	33%	69	376	4,171	0.09	6	34
Williamson River excluding Sprague	358.4	36.0	84.4	25%	26%	20%	100	235	3,702	0.10	10	23
Total Williamson River	738.6	62.4	227.5	51%	46%	53%	84	308	7,873	0.09	8	29

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,179.7	112.9	314.7	82%	83%	73%	96	267	8,362	0.14	13	38
Total Pumped Area Inflows	28.8	8.4	91.9	2%	6%	21%	290	3,186	87	0.33	96	1,058
Ungauged Inflows	234.1	15.2	23.2	16%	11%	5%	65	99	1,034	0.23	15	22
Total External Inflows	1,442.7	136.5	429.8	100%	100%	100%	95	298	9,483	0.15	14	45
Precipitation	103.3	8.8	60.9	7%	6%	14%	85	589	289	0.36	30	211
Evaporation	279.5			19%					289	0.97		
Net Inflow	1,266.5	145.3	490.6	88%	106%	114%	115	387	9,772	0.13	15	50
Lake Outflow	1,378.6	142.3	1,789.3	96%	104%	416%	103	1,298	9,772	0.14	15	183
Storage Increase	-112.1	-52.4	-401.5	-8%	-38%	-93%						
Net Retention	0.0	55.3	-897.2	0%	41%	-209%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,442.7	93.8	142.8	100%	69%	33%	65	99	9,483	0.15	10	15
Anthropogenic		42.7	286.9		31%	67%	30	199	9,483		5	30

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	729.7	479.9	952.3
Area (km ²)	288.9	275.5	296.9
Elevation (ft)	4,140.7	4,137.8	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.7	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.58 years
Net Water Load	4.99 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.47 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	40.5 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2013

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	96.0	11.4	33.7	7%	10%	10%	119	351	96	1.00	119	353
Wood River above Weed Road	259.2	22.8	28.2	20%	19%	9%	88	109	333	0.78	69	85
Wood River below Weed Road	69.6	12.8	20.1	5%	11%	6%	183	288	61	1.15	210	330
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	328.9	35.6	48.3	25%	30%	15%	108	147	394	0.83	90	123
Sprague River	320.9	18.3	87.5	25%	16%	27%	57	273	4,171	0.08	4	21
Williamson River excluding Sprague	319.0	31.5	62.6	25%	27%	19%	99	196	3,702	0.09	9	17
Total Williamson River	639.9	49.8	149.9	49%	42%	46%	78	234	7,873	0.08	6	19

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,064.8	96.8	231.8	82%	82%	71%	91	218	8,362	0.13	12	28
Total Pumped Area Inflows	25.5	7.5	72.2	2%	6%	22%	292	2,825	87	0.29	86	831
Ungauged Inflows	205.4	13.4	20.3	16%	11%	6%	65	99	1,036	0.20	13	20
Total External Inflows	1,295.7	117.6	324.3	100%	100%	100%	91	250	9,485	0.14	12	34
Precipitation	103.8	8.8	60.7	8%	7%	19%	85	585	287	0.36	31	211
Evaporation	288.6			22%					287	1.01		
Net Inflow	1,110.9	126.4	385.0	86%	107%	119%	114	347	9,772	0.11	13	39
Lake Outflow	1,028.3	136.2	1,551.8	79%	116%	478%	132	1,509	9,772	0.11	14	159
Storage Increase	81.3	9.6	67.9	6%	8%	21%						
Net Retention	1.3	-19.3	-1,234.7	0%	-16%	-381%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,295.7	84.2	128.3	100%	72%	40%	65	99	9,485	0.14	9	14
Anthropogenic		33.4	196.1		28%	60%	26	151	9,485		4	21

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	684.9	464.0	881.9
Area (km ²)	286.9	275.0	295.4
Elevation (ft)	4,140.2	4,137.7	4,142.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.4	1.7	3.0

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.62 years
Net Water Load	4.52 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.41 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-16.4 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2014

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	77.9	9.7	31.6	7%	9%	12%	125	405	96	0.81	102	330
Wood River above Weed Road	238.5	21.5	26.0	21%	21%	10%	90	109	333	0.72	65	78
Wood River below Weed Road	64.7	11.7	11.8	6%	11%	5%	181	183	61	1.06	192	195
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	303.3	33.2	37.6	27%	32%	15%	109	124	394	0.77	84	95
Sprague River	249.4	14.8	69.2	22%	14%	27%	59	277	4,171	0.06	4	17
Williamson River excluding Sprague	310.1	29.8	47.0	27%	29%	18%	96	152	3,702	0.08	8	13
Total Williamson River	559.5	44.7	116.0	49%	43%	45%	80	207	7,873	0.07	6	15

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	940.7	87.6	185.1	82%	84%	72%	93	197	8,362	0.11	10	22
Total Pumped Area Inflows	18.0	5.0	52.8	2%	5%	21%	281	2,938	87	0.21	58	608
Ungauged Inflows	182.1	11.8	18.0	16%	11%	7%	65	99	1,036	0.18	11	17
Total External Inflows	1,140.8	104.5	256.0	100%	100%	100%	92	224	9,485	0.12	11	27
Precipitation	91.4	8.3	57.3	8%	8%	22%	91	627	287	0.32	29	200
Evaporation	304.2			27%					287	1.06		
Net Inflow	928.0	112.8	313.3	81%	108%	122%	122	338	9,772	0.09	12	32
Lake Outflow	978.9	137.6	1,439.5	86%	132%	562%	141	1,471	9,772	0.10	14	147
Storage Increase	-50.9	-1.9	-123.7	-4%	-2%	-48%						
Net Retention	0.0	-23.0	-1,002.5	0%	-22%	-392%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,140.8	74.2	112.9	100%	71%	44%	65	99	9,485	0.12	8	12
Anthropogenic		30.3	143.1		29%	56%	27	125	9,485		3	15

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	683.3	494.2	880.1
Area (km ²)	286.6	276.2	295.3
Elevation (ft)	4,140.2	4,138.0	4,142.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.4	1.8	3.0

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.74 years
Net Water Load	3.98 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.36 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-22.0 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2015

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	62.7	7.0	19.8	5%	7%	8%	111	316	96	0.66	73	207
Wood River above Weed Road	230.6	19.5	24.7	20%	19%	10%	85	107	333	0.69	59	74
Wood River below Weed Road	78.0	14.1	20.0	7%	14%	8%	181	257	61	1.28	232	329
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	308.6	33.6	44.7	26%	33%	18%	109	145	394	0.78	85	113
Sprague River	307.0	18.5	95.6	26%	18%	39%	60	312	4,171	0.07	4	23
Williamson River excluding Sprague	287.4	26.8	24.2	24%	26%	10%	93	84	3,702	0.08	7	7
Total Williamson River	594.3	44.9	107.4	50%	43%	44%	75	181	7,873	0.08	6	14

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	965.7	85.5	171.9	82%	83%	70%	89	178	8,362	0.12	10	21
Total Pumped Area Inflows	18.0	5.0	52.8	2%	5%	22%	281	2,938	87	0.21	58	608
Ungauged Inflows	197.8	12.9	19.6	17%	12%	8%	65	99	1,034	0.19	12	19
Total External Inflows	1,181.5	103.4	244.3	100%	100%	100%	87	207	9,483	0.12	11	26
Precipitation	124.2	9.6	66.4	11%	9%	27%	77	534	289	0.43	33	230
Evaporation	301.5			26%					289	1.04		
Net Inflow	1,004.2	113.0	310.7	85%	109%	127%	112	309	9,772	0.10	12	32
Lake Outflow	955.0	131.2	1,339.5	81%	127%	548%	137	1,403	9,772	0.10	13	137
Storage Increase	49.2	19.7	354.6	4%	19%	145%						
Net Retention	0.0	-37.8	-1,383.4	0%	-37%	-566%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,181.5	76.8	117.0	100%	74%	48%	65	99	9,483	0.12	8	12
Anthropogenic		26.6	127.4		26%	52%	22	108	9,483		3	13

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	724.2	490.0	925.2
Area (km ²)	288.5	275.8	296.3
Elevation (ft)	4,140.7	4,138.0	4,142.9
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.8	3.1

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.72 years
Net Water Load	4.10 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.36 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-36.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2016

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	70.9	10.1	32.7	5%	8%	8%	142	461	96	0.74	105	342
Wood River above Weed Road	237.0	21.5	30.7	17%	16%	8%	91	130	333	0.71	65	92
Wood River below Weed Road	67.0	13.9	17.6	5%	10%	4%	208	263	61	1.10	229	290
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	304.1	35.4	47.2	21%	27%	12%	116	155	394	0.77	90	120
Sprague River	445.7	31.1	174.0	31%	23%	43%	70	390	4,171	0.11	7	42
Williamson River excluding Sprague	317.6	33.3	75.9	22%	25%	19%	105	239	3,702	0.09	9	20
Total Williamson River	763.3	64.4	248.9	53%	49%	61%	84	326	7,873	0.10	8	32

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,138.2	109.9	328.8	80%	83%	80%	97	289	8,362	0.14	13	39
Total Pumped Area Inflows	18.3	5.1	53.7	1%	4%	13%	281	2,938	87	0.21	59	618
Ungauged Inflows	270.8	17.6	26.8	19%	13%	7%	65	99	1,035	0.26	17	26
Total External Inflows	1,427.3	132.6	409.3	100%	100%	100%	93	287	9,484	0.15	14	43
Precipitation	126.8	9.7	67.1	9%	7%	16%	77	529	288	0.44	34	233
Evaporation	302.8			21%					288	1.05		
Net Inflow	1,251.3	142.3	476.4	88%	107%	116%	114	381	9,772	0.13	15	49
Lake Outflow	1,298.4	176.6	2,154.9	91%	133%	527%	136	1,660	9,772	0.13	18	221
Storage Increase	-55.1	-18.4	-208.7	-4%	-14%	-51%						
Net Retention	8.0	-15.9	-1,469.8	1%	-12%	-359%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,427.3	92.8	141.3	100%	70%	35%	65	99	9,484	0.15	10	15
Anthropogenic		39.8	268.0		30%	65%	28	188	9,484		4	28

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	718.0	503.5	949.6
Area (km ²)	288.0	277.4	296.9
Elevation (ft)	4,140.6	4,138.1	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.8	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.57 years
Net Water Load	4.96 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.46 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-12.0 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2017

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	184.3	33.1	103.0	9%	16%	15%	180	559	96	1.93	347	1,077
Wood River above Weed Road	306.0	27.4	34.1	15%	13%	5%	90	111	333	0.92	82	102
Wood River below Weed Road	81.5	16.7	17.1	4%	8%	3%	204	210	61	1.34	274	281
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	387.6	44.1	51.1	19%	21%	8%	114	132	394	0.98	112	130
Sprague River	759.0	67.1	287.5	37%	32%	42%	88	379	4,171	0.18	16	69
Williamson River excluding Sprague	397.3	40.1	135.1	19%	19%	20%	101	340	3,702	0.11	11	36
Total Williamson River	1,156.3	106.4	408.0	56%	50%	60%	92	353	7,873	0.15	14	52

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,728.2	183.6	562.1	84%	86%	83%	106	325	8,362	0.21	22	67
Total Pumped Area Inflows	26.2	9.9	86.0	1%	5%	13%	377	3,287	87	0.30	114	991
Ungauged Inflows	292.9	19.0	29.0	14%	9%	4%	65	99	1,034	0.28	18	28
Total External Inflows	2,047.3	212.5	677.2	100%	100%	100%	104	331	9,483	0.22	22	71
Precipitation	160.8	11.0	76.3	8%	5%	11%	69	474	289	0.56	38	264
Evaporation	327.3			16%					289	1.13		
Net Inflow	1,880.8	223.6	753.4	92%	105%	111%	119	401	9,772	0.19	23	77
Lake Outflow	1,823.1	210.0	2,497.3	89%	99%	369%	115	1,370	9,772	0.19	21	256
Storage Increase	57.7	36.3	360.1	3%	17%	53%						
Net Retention	0.0	-22.8	-2,104.0	0%	-11%	-311%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	2,047.3	133.1	202.7	100%	63%	30%	65	99	9,483	0.22	14	21
Anthropogenic		79.5	474.5		37%	70%	39	232	9,483		8	50

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	733.3	499.3	925.2
Area (km ²)	288.9	277.0	296.3
Elevation (ft)	4,140.8	4,138.1	4,142.9
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.8	3.1

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.39 years
Net Water Load	7.09 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.74 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-10.7 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2018

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	74.2	8.5	23.0	6%	7%	8%	115	310	96	0.78	89	241
Wood River above Weed Road	310.5	25.5	32.4	24%	22%	12%	82	104	333	0.93	76	97
Wood River below Weed Road	73.7	11.8	10.0	6%	10%	4%	160	136	61	1.21	194	165
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	384.2	37.3	42.4	30%	32%	15%	97	110	394	0.98	95	108
Sprague River	322.6	20.4	89.7	25%	17%	32%	63	278	4,171	0.08	5	22
Williamson River excluding Sprague	296.7	30.0	30.7	23%	26%	11%	101	103	3,702	0.08	8	8
Total Williamson River	619.3	50.4	118.7	48%	43%	42%	81	192	7,873	0.08	6	15

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,077.6	96.1	184.1	83%	82%	66%	89	171	8,362	0.13	11	22
Total Pumped Area Inflows	22.9	8.5	76.5	2%	7%	27%	372	3,344	87	0.26	98	881
Ungauged Inflows	198.0	12.9	19.6	15%	11%	7%	65	99	1,034	0.19	12	19
Total External Inflows	1,298.5	117.5	280.3	100%	100%	100%	91	216	9,484	0.14	12	30
Precipitation	82.2	8.0	55.0	6%	7%	20%	97	670	288	0.28	28	191
Evaporation	299.7			23%					288	1.04		
Net Inflow	1,081.0	125.5	335.3	83%	107%	120%	116	310	9,772	0.11	13	34
Lake Outflow	1,126.4	165.0	2,185.2	87%	140%	780%	146	1,940	9,772	0.12	17	224
Storage Increase	-50.1	-24.4	-109.6	-4%	-21%	-39%						
Net Retention	4.6	-15.2	-1,740.3	0%	-13%	-621%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,298.5	84.4	128.6	100%	72%	46%	65	99	9,484	0.14	9	14
Anthropogenic		33.1	151.7		28%	54%	26	117	9,484		3	16

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	717.9	511.1	905.3
Area (km ²)	288.5	277.7	295.9
Elevation (ft)	4,140.6	4,138.2	4,142.7
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.8	3.1

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.66 years
Net Water Load	4.50 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.41 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-12.9 %

Table E2: Multi-year mass balance summary tables

Description: Mean annual mass balance summaries of select multi-year periods

Periods:

Group	Start	End	Note
3-Year Periods	1992	1994	
	1995	1997	
	1998	2000	
	2001	2003	
	2004	2006	
	2007	2009	
	2010	2012	
	2013	2015	
	2016	2018	
9-Year Periods	1992	2000	
	2001	2009	
	2010	2018	
Pre/Post TMDL Baseline Period	1992	1998	TMDL Baseline
	1999	2018	post-TMDL Baseline
Dataset Extension	1992	2010	Walker et al., 2012
	2011	2018	Extended Period
Overall	1992	2018	Period of Record

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1992 - 1994 (3-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	78.5	11.3	36.1	6%	8%	8%	144	460	96	0.82	118	378
Wood River above Weed Road	195.9	18.7	29.2	16%	13%	7%	96	149	333	0.59	56	88
Wood River below Weed Road	38.8	11.5	29.9	3%	8%	7%	297	772	61	0.64	189	492
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	219.5	29.5	56.9	18%	21%	13%	134	259	394	0.56	75	145
Sprague River	370.0	32.4	150.8	30%	23%	34%	88	408	4,171	0.09	8	36
Williamson River excluding Sprague	266.7	30.8	56.8	21%	22%	13%	115	213	3,702	0.07	8	15
Total Williamson River	636.7	62.6	202.5	51%	45%	46%	98	318	7,873	0.08	8	26

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	934.7	103.4	295.6	75%	74%	67%	111	316	8,362	0.11	12	35
Total Pumped Area Inflows	48.3	19.6	118.8	4%	14%	27%	406	2,459	107	0.45	184	1,114
Ungauged Inflows	265.7	17.3	26.3	21%	12%	6%	65	99	1,033	0.26	17	25
Total External Inflows	1,248.7	140.2	440.7	100%	100%	100%	112	353	9,502	0.13	15	46
Precipitation	108.6	8.7	60.1	9%	6%	14%	80	553	270	0.40	32	222
Evaporation	270.1			22%					270	1.00		
Net Inflow	1,087.3	148.9	500.8	87%	106%	114%	137	461	9,772	0.11	15	51
Lake Outflow	1,121.7	119.9	1,767.1	90%	86%	401%	107	1,575	9,772	0.11	12	181
Storage Increase	-36.7	-26.1	-269.8	-3%	-19%	-61%						
Net Retention	2.2	55.1	-996.5	0%	39%	-226%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,248.7	81.2	123.6	100%	58%	28%	65	99	9,502	0.13	9	13
Anthropogenic		59.1	317.1		42%	72%	47	254	9,502		6	33

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	661.2	387.6	925.9
Area (km ²)	269.9	262.9	273.3
Elevation (ft)	4,140.2	4,136.8	4,143.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.4	1.5	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.61 years
Net Water Load	4.63 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.52 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	39.3 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1995 - 1997 (3-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				
Gauged Tributary Inflows												
Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	137.9	19.9	66.2	7%	10%	9%	144	480	96	1.44	208	692
Wood River above Weed Road	282.6	22.7	45.6	14%	11%	6%	80	161	333	0.85	68	137
Wood River below Weed Road	53.8	16.6	41.3	3%	8%	5%	309	769	61	0.88	273	680
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	330.0	39.2	84.0	17%	19%	11%	119	254	394	0.84	99	213
Sprague River	761.4	60.8	298.6	39%	30%	40%	80	392	4,171	0.18	15	72
Williamson River excluding Sprague	336.1	39.9	147.9	17%	20%	20%	119	440	3,702	0.09	11	40
Total Williamson River	1,097.5	100.0	440.5	56%	49%	58%	91	401	7,873	0.14	13	56

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,565.3	159.1	590.7	80%	78%	78%	102	377	8,362	0.19	19	71
Total Pumped Area Inflows	53.0	21.5	130.3	3%	11%	17%	406	2,459	107	0.50	202	1,221
Ungauged Inflows	341.0	22.2	33.8	17%	11%	4%	65	99	1,032	0.33	21	33
Total External Inflows	1,959.3	202.7	754.7	100%	100%	100%	103	385	9,501	0.21	21	79
Precipitation	166.9	11.0	75.9	9%	5%	10%	66	455	271	0.62	41	280
Evaporation	250.0			13%					271	0.92		
Net Inflow	1,876.3	213.7	830.6	96%	105%	110%	114	443	9,772	0.19	22	85
Lake Outflow	1,784.1	185.5	2,734.0	91%	91%	362%	104	1,532	9,772	0.18	19	280
Storage Increase	91.5	22.0	269.8	5%	11%	36%						
Net Retention	0.7	6.3	-2,173.3	0%	3%	-288%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,959.3	127.4	194.0	100%	63%	26%	65	99	9,501	0.21	13	20
Anthropogenic		75.4	560.7		37%	74%	38	286	9,501		8	59

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	740.5	385.2	921.8
Area (km ²)	271.1	262.7	273.3
Elevation (ft)	4,141.1	4,136.8	4,143.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.7	1.5	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.39 years
Net Water Load	7.23 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.75 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	3.1 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1998 - 2000 (3-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	133.6	16.4	53.9	6%	8%	7%	123	404	96	1.40	171	564
Wood River above Weed Road	274.9	22.6	34.4	13%	11%	5%	82	125	333	0.83	68	103
Wood River below Weed Road	95.4	16.0	27.1	5%	8%	4%	167	284	61	1.57	263	446
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	370.0	38.6	61.5	18%	19%	8%	104	166	394	0.94	98	156
Sprague River	696.9	52.0	228.4	33%	25%	31%	75	328	4,171	0.17	12	55
Williamson River excluding Sprague	461.1	44.9	197.5	22%	22%	27%	97	428	3,702	0.12	12	53
Total Williamson River	1,158.0	96.9	425.8	55%	47%	59%	84	368	7,873	0.15	12	54

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,661.6	151.9	541.2	79%	73%	75%	91	326	8,362	0.20	18	65
Total Pumped Area Inflows	51.1	30.8	147.3	2%	15%	20%	603	2,881	97	0.53	328	1,545
Ungauged Inflows	379.4	24.7	37.6	18%	12%	5%	65	99	1,041	0.36	24	36
Total External Inflows	2,092.1	207.4	726.1	100%	100%	100%	99	347	9,500	0.22	22	76
Precipitation	122.9	9.3	64.2	6%	4%	9%	76	522	272	0.45	34	236
Evaporation	244.9			12%					272	0.90		
Net Inflow	1,970.0	216.7	790.2	94%	104%	109%	110	401	9,772	0.20	22	81
Lake Outflow	1,987.4	222.8	2,744.1	95%	107%	378%	112	1,381	9,772	0.20	23	281
Storage Increase	-17.6	-1.6	-13.8	-1%	-1%	-2%						
Net Retention	0.2	-4.5	-1,940.1	0%	-2%	-267%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	2,092.1	136.0	207.1	100%	66%	29%	65	99	9,500	0.22	14	22
Anthropogenic		71.4	518.9		34%	71%	34	248	9,500		8	55

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	777.6	589.6	930.9
Area (km ²)	272.1	268.0	273.3
Elevation (ft)	4,141.6	4,139.3	4,143.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.9	2.2	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.39 years
Net Water Load	7.69 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.76 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-2.2 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2001 - 2003 (3-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	76.3	10.7	34.0	6%	8%	8%	140	445	96	0.80	112	355
Wood River above Weed Road	201.9	17.2	24.6	15%	13%	6%	85	122	333	0.61	52	74
Wood River below Weed Road	92.0	13.5	19.2	7%	10%	4%	146	208	61	1.51	222	315
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	293.7	30.7	43.5	22%	23%	10%	104	148	394	0.75	78	111
Sprague River	336.4	22.2	94.0	25%	16%	21%	66	279	4,171	0.08	5	23
Williamson River excluding Sprague	347.6	33.3	147.9	26%	25%	33%	96	425	3,702	0.09	9	40
Total Williamson River	684.0	55.5	241.3	51%	41%	54%	81	353	7,873	0.09	7	31

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,054.0	96.9	318.8	79%	72%	72%	92	302	8,362	0.13	12	38
Total Pumped Area Inflows	34.6	21.6	100.1	3%	16%	23%	624	2,898	87	0.40	248	1,153
Ungauged Inflows	247.2	16.1	24.5	19%	12%	6%	65	99	1,051	0.24	15	23
Total External Inflows	1,335.8	134.5	443.4	100%	100%	100%	101	332	9,501	0.14	14	47
Precipitation	93.6	8.1	56.2	7%	6%	13%	87	600	271	0.35	30	207
Evaporation	278.0			21%					271	1.02		
Net Inflow	1,151.5	142.7	499.5	86%	106%	113%	124	434	9,772	0.12	15	51
Lake Outflow	1,154.6	128.6	2,180.9	86%	96%	492%	111	1,889	9,772	0.12	13	223
Storage Increase	-15.0	6.6	88.2	-1%	5%	20%						
Net Retention	11.9	7.5	-1,769.5	1%	6%	-399%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,335.8	86.8	132.2	100%	65%	30%	65	99	9,501	0.14	9	14
Anthropogenic		47.7	311.1		35%	70%	36	233	9,501		5	33

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	739.2	522.8	918.4
Area (km ²)	271.3	266.8	273.2
Elevation (ft)	4,141.1	4,138.5	4,143.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.7	2.0	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.64 years
Net Water Load	4.92 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.50 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	5.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2004 - 2006 (3-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	101.0	15.7	58.9	6%	9%	10%	156	584	96	1.06	165	616
Wood River above Weed Road	221.6	19.2	30.8	14%	12%	5%	87	139	333	0.67	58	92
Wood River below Weed Road	101.2	17.7	32.0	6%	11%	5%	175	316	61	1.66	291	527
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	322.7	36.9	62.8	20%	22%	10%	114	195	394	0.82	94	159
Sprague River	530.5	43.7	203.2	33%	26%	34%	82	383	4,171	0.13	10	49
Williamson River excluding Sprague	316.0	33.6	130.1	20%	20%	22%	106	412	3,702	0.09	9	35
Total Williamson River	846.4	77.3	329.1	53%	46%	55%	91	389	7,873	0.11	10	42

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,270.1	129.9	450.8	79%	78%	75%	102	355	8,362	0.15	16	54
Total Pumped Area Inflows	40.2	17.4	121.0	2%	10%	20%	433	3,010	86	0.47	202	1,404
Ungauged Inflows	299.8	19.5	29.7	19%	12%	5%	65	99	1,052	0.29	19	28
Total External Inflows	1,610.1	166.8	601.5	100%	100%	100%	104	374	9,500	0.17	18	63
Precipitation	113.5	8.9	61.6	7%	5%	10%	79	543	272	0.42	33	227
Evaporation	255.4			16%					272	0.94		
Net Inflow	1,468.3	175.7	663.1	91%	105%	110%	120	452	9,772	0.15	18	68
Lake Outflow	1,468.1	149.9	2,453.1	91%	90%	408%	102	1,671	9,772	0.15	15	251
Storage Increase	-6.5	4.9	23.7	0%	3%	4%						
Net Retention	6.8	20.9	-1,813.8	0%	13%	-302%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,610.1	104.7	159.4	100%	63%	26%	65	99	9,500	0.17	11	17
Anthropogenic		62.2	442.1		37%	74%	39	275	9,500		7	47

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	733.8	536.6	918.4
Area (km ²)	271.8	267.0	282.2
Elevation (ft)	4,141.1	4,138.7	4,143.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.7	2.0	3.3

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.50 years
Net Water Load	5.92 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.61 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	12.5 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2007 - 2009 (3-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	101.3	15.5	51.0	7%	11%	11%	153	504	96	1.06	162	533
Wood River above Weed Road	252.7	21.3	31.5	17%	15%	7%	84	125	333	0.76	64	95
Wood River below Weed Road	113.4	18.2	33.2	8%	13%	7%	160	293	61	1.86	299	546
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	366.1	39.4	64.5	25%	28%	14%	108	176	394	0.93	100	164
Sprague River	387.3	25.4	126.5	26%	18%	27%	66	327	4,171	0.09	6	30
Williamson River excluding Sprague	340.8	31.8	93.7	23%	23%	20%	93	275	3,702	0.09	9	25
Total Williamson River	728.1	57.3	220.2	49%	41%	47%	79	302	7,873	0.09	7	28

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,195.5	112.2	335.7	80%	80%	71%	94	281	8,362	0.14	13	40
Total Pumped Area Inflows	43.1	12.0	110.7	3%	9%	24%	278	2,570	84	0.51	145	1,327
Ungauged Inflows	247.1	16.1	24.5	17%	11%	5%	65	99	1,042	0.24	15	23
Total External Inflows	1,485.7	140.2	470.9	100%	100%	100%	94	317	9,489	0.16	15	50
Precipitation	106.6	8.8	61.0	7%	6%	13%	83	573	283	0.38	31	215
Evaporation	270.2			18%					283	0.95		
Net Inflow	1,322.1	149.1	531.9	89%	106%	113%	113	402	9,772	0.14	15	54
Lake Outflow	1,330.7	189.5	2,775.2	90%	135%	589%	142	2,085	9,772	0.14	19	284
Storage Increase	-13.2	-19.8	-138.9	-1%	-14%	-29%						
Net Retention	4.5	-20.6	-2,104.4	0%	-15%	-447%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,485.7	96.6	147.1	100%	69%	31%	65	99	9,489	0.16	10	16
Anthropogenic		43.7	323.8		31%	69%	29	218	9,489		5	34

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	719.9	497.6	939.3
Area (km ²)	283.4	266.4	296.0
Elevation (ft)	4,140.7	4,138.2	4,143.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.9	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.54 years
Net Water Load	5.24 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.49 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-14.7 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2010 - 2012 (3-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	95.1	12.4	43.6	6%	9%	10%	130	459	96	0.99	130	456
Wood River above Weed Road	261.7	23.4	29.6	18%	16%	7%	89	113	333	0.79	70	89
Wood River below Weed Road	88.3	15.1	28.0	6%	10%	6%	171	318	61	1.45	249	461
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	348.0	38.4	57.4	23%	27%	13%	110	165	394	0.88	98	146
Sprague River	447.7	32.2	162.4	30%	22%	36%	72	363	4,171	0.11	8	39
Williamson River excluding Sprague	331.1	34.5	69.6	22%	24%	15%	104	210	3,702	0.09	9	19
Total Williamson River	778.8	66.7	231.2	52%	46%	51%	86	297	7,873	0.10	8	29

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,221.8	117.5	332.3	82%	81%	74%	96	272	8,362	0.15	14	40
Total Pumped Area Inflows	30.7	11.5	95.8	2%	8%	21%	373	3,121	87	0.35	132	1,103
Ungauged Inflows	241.0	15.7	23.9	16%	11%	5%	65	99	1,035	0.23	15	23
Total External Inflows	1,493.5	144.7	452.0	100%	100%	100%	97	303	9,484	0.16	15	48
Precipitation	113.9	9.2	63.6	8%	6%	14%	81	558	288	0.39	32	221
Evaporation	267.3			18%					288	0.93		
Net Inflow	1,340.2	153.9	515.6	90%	106%	114%	115	385	9,772	0.14	16	53
Lake Outflow	1,348.9	124.8	1,800.1	90%	86%	398%	93	1,335	9,772	0.14	13	184
Storage Increase	-8.7	-15.6	-232.3	-1%	-11%	-51%						
Net Retention	0.0	44.6	-1,052.3	0%	31%	-233%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,493.5	97.1	147.9	100%	67%	33%	65	99	9,484	0.16	10	16
Anthropogenic		47.6	304.1		33%	67%	32	204	9,484		5	32

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	713.4	479.0	952.3
Area (km ²)	288.1	275.4	296.9
Elevation (ft)	4,140.5	4,137.8	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.7	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.53 years
Net Water Load	5.18 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.50 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	30.8 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2013 - 2015 (3-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	78.9	9.4	28.4	7%	9%	10%	119	360	96	0.82	98	297
Wood River above Weed Road	242.8	21.3	26.3	20%	20%	10%	88	108	333	0.73	64	79
Wood River below Weed Road	70.8	12.9	17.3	6%	12%	6%	182	245	61	1.16	212	285
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	313.6	34.1	43.5	26%	31%	16%	109	139	394	0.80	87	110
Sprague River	292.4	17.2	84.1	24%	16%	31%	59	288	4,171	0.07	4	20
Williamson River excluding Sprague	305.5	29.4	44.6	25%	27%	16%	96	146	3,702	0.08	8	12
Total Williamson River	597.9	46.5	124.4	50%	43%	45%	78	208	7,873	0.08	6	16

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	990.4	90.0	196.3	82%	83%	71%	91	198	8,362	0.12	11	23
Total Pumped Area Inflows	20.5	5.9	59.3	2%	5%	22%	285	2,891	87	0.24	67	683
Ungauged Inflows	195.1	12.7	19.3	16%	12%	7%	65	99	1,035	0.19	12	19
Total External Inflows	1,206.0	108.5	274.9	100%	100%	100%	90	228	9,485	0.13	11	29
Precipitation	106.5	8.9	61.4	9%	8%	22%	84	577	287	0.37	31	214
Evaporation	298.1			25%					287	1.04		
Net Inflow	1,014.4	117.4	336.3	84%	108%	122%	116	332	9,772	0.10	12	34
Lake Outflow	987.4	135.0	1,443.6	82%	124%	525%	137	1,462	9,772	0.10	14	148
Storage Increase	26.5	9.1	99.6	2%	8%	36%						
Net Retention	0.4	-26.7	-1,206.9	0%	-25%	-439%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,206.0	78.4	119.4	100%	72%	43%	65	99	9,485	0.13	8	13
Anthropogenic		30.1	155.5		28%	57%	25	129	9,485		3	16

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	697.5	464.0	925.2
Area (km ²)	287.4	275.0	296.3
Elevation (ft)	4,140.4	4,137.7	4,142.9
Mean Depth (meters)	2.4	1.7	3.1

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.69 years
Net Water Load	4.20 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.38 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-24.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2016 - 2018 (3-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				
Gauged Tributary Inflows												
Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	109.8	17.3	52.9	7%	11%	12%	157	482	96	1.15	180	553
Wood River above Weed Road	284.5	24.8	32.4	18%	16%	7%	87	114	333	0.85	74	97
Wood River below Weed Road	74.1	14.1	14.9	5%	9%	3%	191	202	61	1.22	232	246
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	358.6	38.9	46.9	23%	25%	10%	108	131	394	0.91	99	119
Sprague River	509.1	39.5	183.7	32%	26%	40%	78	361	4,171	0.12	9	44
Williamson River excluding Sprague	337.2	34.5	80.6	21%	22%	18%	102	239	3,702	0.09	9	22
Total Williamson River	846.3	73.7	258.5	53%	48%	57%	87	305	7,873	0.11	9	33

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,314.7	129.9	358.4	83%	84%	79%	99	273	8,362	0.16	16	43
Total Pumped Area Inflows	22.4	7.8	72.1	1%	5%	16%	349	3,212	87	0.26	90	830
Ungauged Inflows	253.9	16.5	25.1	16%	11%	6%	65	99	1,034	0.25	16	24
Total External Inflows	1,591.0	154.2	455.6	100%	100%	100%	97	286	9,484	0.17	16	48
Precipitation	123.3	9.6	66.1	8%	6%	15%	78	536	288	0.43	33	229
Evaporation	309.9			19%					288	1.07		
Net Inflow	1,404.4	163.8	521.7	88%	106%	115%	117	371	9,772	0.14	17	53
Lake Outflow	1,416.0	183.9	2,279.1	89%	119%	500%	130	1,610	9,772	0.14	19	233
Storage Increase	-15.8	-2.1	13.9	-1%	-1%	3%						
Net Retention	4.2	-17.9	-1,771.4	0%	-12%	-389%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,591.0	103.4	157.5	100%	67%	35%	65	99	9,484	0.17	11	17
Anthropogenic		50.8	298.1		33%	65%	32	187	9,484		5	31

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	723.0	499.3	949.6
Area (km ²)	288.4	277.0	296.9
Elevation (ft)	4,140.6	4,138.1	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.8	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.51 years
Net Water Load	5.52 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.53 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-11.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1992 - 2000 (9-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	116.6	15.8	52.1	7%	9%	8%	136	446	96	1.22	166	545
Wood River above Weed Road	251.1	21.3	36.4	14%	12%	6%	85	145	333	0.75	64	109
Wood River below Weed Road	62.7	14.7	32.8	4%	8%	5%	235	523	61	1.03	242	539
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	306.5	35.7	67.5	17%	19%	11%	117	220	394	0.78	91	171
Sprague River	609.4	48.4	225.9	34%	26%	35%	79	371	4,171	0.15	12	54
Williamson River excluding Sprague	354.6	38.5	134.1	20%	21%	21%	109	378	3,702	0.10	10	36
Total Williamson River	964.0	86.5	356.3	55%	47%	56%	90	370	7,873	0.12	11	45

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,387.2	138.1	475.8	79%	75%	74%	100	343	8,362	0.17	17	57
Total Pumped Area Inflows	50.8	24.0	132.1	3%	13%	21%	472	2,601	103	0.49	238	1,293
Ungauged Inflows	328.7	21.4	32.5	19%	12%	5%	65	99	1,035	0.32	21	31
Total External Inflows	1,766.7	183.5	640.5	100%	100%	100%	104	363	9,501	0.19	19	67
Precipitation	132.8	9.7	66.7	8%	5%	10%	73	502	271	0.49	36	246
Evaporation	255.0			14%					271	0.94		
Net Inflow	1,644.5	193.1	707.2	93%	105%	110%	117	430	9,772	0.17	20	72
Lake Outflow	1,631.1	176.1	2,415.0	92%	96%	377%	108	1,481	9,772	0.17	18	247
Storage Increase	12.4	-1.9	-4.6	1%	-1%	-1%						
Net Retention	1.0	19.0	-1,703.3	0%	10%	-266%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,766.7	114.8	174.9	100%	63%	27%	65	99	9,501	0.19	12	18
Anthropogenic		68.6	465.6		37%	73%	39	264	9,501		7	49

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	726.5	385.2	930.9
Area (km ²)	271.1	262.7	273.3
Elevation (ft)	4,141.0	4,136.8	4,143.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.7	1.5	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.44 years
Net Water Load	6.52 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.68 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	10.3 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2001 - 2009 (9-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	92.9	14.0	48.0	6%	9%	9%	151	517	96	0.97	146	502
Wood River above Weed Road	225.4	19.2	29.0	15%	13%	6%	85	129	333	0.68	58	87
Wood River below Weed Road	102.2	16.4	28.1	7%	11%	6%	161	275	61	1.68	270	463
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	327.5	35.7	57.0	22%	24%	11%	109	174	394	0.83	91	145
Sprague River	418.1	30.4	141.2	28%	21%	28%	73	338	4,171	0.10	7	34
Williamson River excluding Sprague	334.8	32.9	123.9	23%	22%	25%	98	370	3,702	0.09	9	33
Total Williamson River	752.8	63.4	263.5	51%	43%	52%	84	350	7,873	0.10	8	33

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,173.2	113.0	368.4	79%	77%	73%	96	314	8,362	0.14	14	44
Total Pumped Area Inflows	39.3	17.0	110.6	3%	12%	22%	432	2,816	86	0.46	198	1,295
Ungauged Inflows	264.7	17.2	26.2	18%	12%	5%	65	99	1,048	0.25	16	25
Total External Inflows	1,477.2	147.2	505.3	100%	100%	100%	100	342	9,497	0.16	16	53
Precipitation	104.6	8.6	59.6	7%	6%	12%	82	570	275	0.38	31	216
Evaporation	267.9			18%					275	0.97		
Net Inflow	1,313.9	155.8	564.9	89%	106%	112%	119	430	9,772	0.13	16	58
Lake Outflow	1,317.8	156.0	2,469.8	89%	106%	489%	118	1,874	9,772	0.13	16	253
Storage Increase	-11.6	-2.8	-9.0	-1%	-2%	-2%						
Net Retention	7.7	2.6	-1,895.9	1%	2%	-375%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,477.2	96.0	146.2	100%	65%	29%	65	99	9,497	0.16	10	15
Anthropogenic		51.2	359.0		35%	71%	35	243	9,497		5	38

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	731.0	497.6	939.3
Area (km ²)	275.5	266.4	296.0
Elevation (ft)	4,141.0	4,138.2	4,143.3
Mean Depth (meters)	2.7	1.9	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.56 years
Net Water Load	5.36 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.53 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	1.8 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2010 - 2018 (9-Yr Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				
Gauged Tributary Inflows												
Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	94.6	13.0	41.6	7%	10%	11%	137	440	96	0.99	136	435
Wood River above Weed Road	263.0	23.2	29.4	18%	17%	7%	88	112	333	0.79	70	88
Wood River below Weed Road	77.7	14.0	20.1	5%	10%	5%	181	259	61	1.28	231	330
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	340.1	37.2	49.3	24%	27%	13%	109	145	394	0.86	94	125
Sprague River	416.4	29.6	143.4	29%	22%	36%	71	344	4,171	0.10	7	34
Williamson River excluding Sprague	324.6	32.8	64.9	23%	24%	16%	101	200	3,702	0.09	9	18
Total Williamson River	741.0	62.3	204.7	52%	46%	52%	84	276	7,873	0.09	8	26

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,175.6	112.5	295.7	82%	83%	75%	96	251	8,362	0.14	13	35
Total Pumped Area Inflows	24.5	8.4	75.7	2%	6%	19%	341	3,085	87	0.28	97	872
Ungauged Inflows	230.0	15.0	22.8	16%	11%	6%	65	99	1,035	0.22	14	22
Total External Inflows	1,430.2	135.8	394.2	100%	100%	100%	95	276	9,484	0.15	14	42
Precipitation	114.6	9.2	63.7	8%	7%	16%	80	556	288	0.40	32	221
Evaporation	291.8			20%					288	1.01		
Net Inflow	1,253.0	145.0	457.9	88%	107%	116%	116	365	9,772	0.13	15	47
Lake Outflow	1,250.8	147.9	1,841.0	87%	109%	467%	118	1,472	9,772	0.13	15	188
Storage Increase	0.7	-2.9	-39.6	0%	-2%	-10%						
Net Retention	1.5	0.0	-1,343.5	0%	0%	-341%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,430.2	93.0	141.6	100%	68%	36%	65	99	9,484	0.15	10	15
Anthropogenic		42.8	252.6		32%	64%	30	177	9,484		5	27

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	711.3	464.0	952.3
Area (km ²)	288.0	275.0	296.9
Elevation (ft)	4,140.5	4,137.7	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.7	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.57 years
Net Water Load	4.97 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.47 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	0.0 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1992 - 1998 (TMDL Baseline)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	116.5	16.0	53.6	7%	9%	9%	138	460	96	1.22	168	561
Wood River above Weed Road	252.2	21.5	38.2	15%	12%	6%	85	151	333	0.76	65	115
Wood River below Weed Road	50.0	13.8	33.6	3%	8%	5%	277	671	61	0.82	228	552
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	292.9	35.0	69.5	17%	20%	11%	119	237	394	0.74	89	176
Sprague River	595.5	47.9	231.9	36%	27%	37%	81	389	4,171	0.14	11	56
Williamson River excluding Sprague	320.3	37.8	121.4	19%	21%	19%	118	379	3,702	0.09	10	33
Total Williamson River	915.8	85.2	348.5	55%	48%	56%	93	380	7,873	0.12	11	44

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,325.3	136.3	471.6	79%	77%	75%	103	356	8,362	0.16	16	56
Total Pumped Area Inflows	50.7	20.4	124.3	3%	12%	20%	403	2,454	106	0.48	192	1,171
Ungauged Inflows	300.3	19.5	29.7	18%	11%	5%	65	99	1,033	0.29	19	29
Total External Inflows	1,676.3	176.2	625.6	100%	100%	100%	105	373	9,501	0.18	19	66
Precipitation	138.0	9.9	68.1	8%	6%	11%	71	493	271	0.51	36	251
Evaporation	256.0			15%					271	0.95		
Net Inflow	1,558.4	186.1	693.7	93%	106%	111%	119	445	9,772	0.16	19	71
Lake Outflow	1,536.0	158.4	2,304.6	92%	90%	368%	103	1,500	9,772	0.16	16	236
Storage Increase	21.0	-3.4	-37.7	1%	-2%	-6%						
Net Retention	1.3	31.1	-1,573.2	0%	18%	-251%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,676.3	109.0	166.0	100%	62%	27%	65	99	9,501	0.18	11	17
Anthropogenic		67.3	459.7		38%	73%	40	274	9,501		7	48

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	713.9	385.2	925.9
Area (km ²)	270.8	262.7	273.3
Elevation (ft)	4,140.8	4,136.8	4,143.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.6	1.5	3.4

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.46 years
Net Water Load	6.19 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.65 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	17.7 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1999 - 2018 (Post-TMDL Baseline)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	96.0	13.7	45.0	6%	9%	9%	142	469	96	1.00	143	471
Wood River above Weed Road	244.5	21.2	29.3	16%	14%	6%	87	120	333	0.73	63	88
Wood River below Weed Road	91.6	15.5	24.7	6%	10%	5%	169	270	61	1.51	255	406
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	335.8	36.6	53.8	22%	25%	11%	109	160	394	0.85	93	137
Sprague River	441.3	32.0	148.6	29%	22%	31%	73	337	4,171	0.11	8	36
Williamson River excluding Sprague	344.2	33.7	102.8	23%	23%	22%	98	299	3,702	0.09	9	28
Total Williamson River	785.5	65.6	249.1	52%	44%	53%	84	317	7,873	0.10	8	32

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,217.4	115.9	347.9	80%	78%	73%	95	286	8,362	0.15	14	42
Total Pumped Area Inflows	33.8	15.1	99.8	2%	10%	21%	445	2,948	87	0.39	172	1,147
Ungauged Inflows	265.4	17.3	26.3	18%	12%	6%	65	99	1,042	0.25	17	25
Total External Inflows	1,516.6	148.2	474.0	100%	100%	100%	98	313	9,491	0.16	16	50
Precipitation	110.1	8.9	61.7	7%	6%	13%	81	560	281	0.39	32	220
Evaporation	277.0			18%					281	0.99		
Net Inflow	1,349.7	157.2	535.7	89%	106%	113%	116	397	9,772	0.14	16	55
Lake Outflow	1,352.2	160.6	2,220.0	89%	108%	468%	119	1,642	9,772	0.14	16	227
Storage Increase	-6.7	-2.2	-10.7	0%	-1%	-2%						
Net Retention	4.2	-1.2	-1,673.6	0%	-1%	-353%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,516.6	98.6	150.1	100%	67%	32%	65	99	9,491	0.16	10	16
Anthropogenic		49.6	323.8		33%	68%	33	214	9,491		5	34

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	726.0	464.0	952.3
Area (km ²)	280.8	266.4	296.9
Elevation (ft)	4,140.8	4,137.7	4,143.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.6	1.7	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.54 years
Net Water Load	5.40 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.53 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-0.8 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1992 - 2010 (Walker et al. 2012)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	104.9	14.9	49.8	7%	9%	9%	142	474	96	1.10	156	520
Wood River above Weed Road	238.1	20.3	32.4	15%	12%	6%	85	136	333	0.71	61	97
Wood River below Weed Road	82.6	15.4	30.0	5%	9%	5%	186	364	61	1.36	253	494
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	317.2	35.6	61.5	20%	22%	11%	112	194	394	0.81	90	156
Sprague River	501.6	38.3	177.9	31%	24%	32%	76	355	4,171	0.12	9	43
Williamson River excluding Sprague	343.7	35.5	125.2	21%	22%	22%	103	364	3,702	0.09	10	34
Total Williamson River	845.3	73.6	300.6	53%	45%	54%	87	356	7,873	0.11	9	38

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,267.4	124.0	411.8	79%	76%	74%	98	325	8,362	0.15	15	49
Total Pumped Area Inflows	43.6	19.7	117.8	3%	12%	21%	451	2,700	94	0.46	210	1,258
Ungauged Inflows	291.1	18.9	28.8	18%	12%	5%	65	99	1,042	0.28	18	28
Total External Inflows	1,602.1	162.6	558.4	100%	100%	100%	101	349	9,498	0.17	17	59
Precipitation	117.5	9.1	62.9	7%	6%	11%	77	535	274	0.43	33	230
Evaporation	261.6			16%					274	0.96		
Net Inflow	1,458.0	171.7	621.3	91%	106%	111%	118	426	9,772	0.15	18	64
Lake Outflow	1,450.2	162.4	2,402.6	91%	100%	430%	112	1,657	9,772	0.15	17	246
Storage Increase	3.6	-1.4	-0.8	0%	-1%	0%						
Net Retention	4.1	10.8	-1,780.4	0%	7%	-319%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,602.1	104.1	158.6	100%	64%	28%	65	99	9,498	0.17	11	17
Anthropogenic		58.5	399.8		36%	72%	36	250	9,498		6	42

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	724.1	385.2	939.3
Area (km ²)	273.9	262.7	296.0
Elevation (ft)	4,140.9	4,136.8	4,143.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.6	1.5	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.50 years
Net Water Load	5.85 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.59 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	6.6 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 2011 - 2018 (Extended Period)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				
Gauged Tributary Inflows												
Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	92.8	12.9	41.2	6%	9%	10%	139	444	96	0.97	135	431
Wood River above Weed Road	266.5	23.5	29.8	18%	17%	7%	88	112	333	0.80	71	89
Wood River below Weed Road	76.7	14.2	19.8	5%	10%	5%	186	258	61	1.26	234	325
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	342.5	37.7	49.3	24%	27%	12%	110	144	394	0.87	96	125
Sprague River	433.0	31.1	151.9	30%	22%	37%	72	351	4,171	0.10	7	36
Williamson River excluding Sprague	324.5	32.9	65.9	22%	24%	16%	101	203	3,702	0.09	9	18
Total Williamson River	757.6	63.9	213.7	52%	46%	53%	84	282	7,873	0.10	8	27

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,192.9	114.5	304.3	82%	83%	75%	96	255	8,362	0.14	14	36
Total Pumped Area Inflows	25.4	8.8	78.6	2%	6%	19%	347	3,098	87	0.29	101	905
Ungauged Inflows	235.1	15.3	23.3	16%	11%	6%	65	99	1,034	0.23	15	23
Total External Inflows	1,453.4	138.6	406.1	100%	100%	100%	95	279	9,484	0.15	15	43
Precipitation	116.9	9.3	64.4	8%	7%	16%	80	551	288	0.41	32	223
Evaporation	295.2			20%					288	1.02		
Net Inflow	1,275.1	147.9	470.5	88%	107%	116%	116	369	9,772	0.13	15	48
Lake Outflow	1,280.3	154.3	1,860.4	88%	111%	458%	121	1,453	9,772	0.13	16	190
Storage Increase	-6.9	-5.1	-58.0	0%	-4%	-14%						
Net Retention	1.7	-1.3	-1,332.0	0%	-1%	-328%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,453.4	94.5	143.9	100%	68%	35%	65	99	9,484	0.15	10	15
Anthropogenic		44.1	262.2		32%	65%	30	180	9,484		5	28

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	720.1	464.0	952.3
Area (km ²)	288.3	275.0	296.9
Elevation (ft)	4,140.6	4,137.7	4,143.2
Mean Depth (meters)	2.5	1.7	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.56 years
Net Water Load	5.04 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.48 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	-1.0 %

Upper Klamath Lake Water & Nutrient Balances

Water Year(s): 1992 - 2018 (Period of Record)

Term	Flow hm ³ /yr	Nutrient Loads		Fraction of Total External Inflow			Nutrient Concs		Dr. Area km ²	Runoff m/yr	P Export kg/km ²	N Export kg/km ²
		TP mt/y	TN mt/y	Flow	TP Load	TN Load	TP ppb	TN ppb				

Gauged Tributary Inflows

Sevenmile Canal at Dike Rd	101.4	14.3	47.2	7%	9%	9%	141	466	96	1.06	149	494
Wood River above Weed Road	246.5	21.2	31.6	16%	14%	6%	86	128	333	0.74	64	95
Wood River below Weed Road	80.9	15.1	27.0	5%	10%	5%	186	334	61	1.33	248	444
Total Wood River at Dike Rd	324.7	36.2	57.9	21%	23%	11%	111	178	394	0.82	92	147
Sprague River	481.3	36.2	170.2	31%	23%	33%	75	354	4,171	0.12	9	41
Williamson River excluding Sprague	338.0	34.8	107.6	22%	22%	21%	103	318	3,702	0.09	9	29
Total Williamson River	819.3	70.7	274.8	53%	45%	54%	86	335	7,873	0.10	9	35

Overall Balance

Total Gauged Tributary Inflows	1,245.3	121.2	380.0	80%	78%	74%	97	305	8,362	0.15	14	45
Total Pumped Area Inflows	38.2	16.4	106.2	2%	11%	21%	430	2,778	92	0.41	178	1,153
Ungauged Inflows	274.5	17.8	27.2	18%	11%	5%	65	99	1,040	0.26	17	26
Total External Inflows	1,558.0	155.5	513.3	100%	100%	100%	100	329	9,494	0.16	16	54
Precipitation	117.3	9.2	63.3	8%	6%	12%	78	540	278	0.42	33	228
Evaporation	271.5			17%					278	0.98		
Net Inflow	1,403.8	164.7	576.6	90%	106%	112%	117	411	9,772	0.14	17	59
Lake Outflow	1,399.9	160.0	2,241.9	90%	103%	437%	114	1,602	9,772	0.14	16	229
Storage Increase	0.5	-2.5	-17.7	0%	-2%	-3%						
Net Retention	3.4	7.2	-1,647.6	0%	5%	-321%						

Natural Background vs. Anthropogenic Loads

Background / Natural	1,558.0	101.3	154.2	100%	65%	30%	65	99	9,494	0.16	11	16
Anthropogenic		54.2	359.0		35%	70%	35	230	9,494		6	38

Morphometry

	Mean	Min	Max
Volume (hm ³)	722.9	385.2	952.3
Area (km ²)	278.2	262.7	296.9
Elevation (ft)	4,140.8	4,136.8	4,143.4
Mean Depth (meters)	2.6	1.5	3.2

Phosphorus Model Parameters

Hydraulic Residence Time	0.51 years
Net Water Load	5.60 m/yr
Areal Total P Load	0.56 g/m ² -yr
Total P Retention Coefficient	4.6 %

Appendix F

Inflow/Outflow Total Phosphorus Loading Dynamics

Table F1 Linear regression model coefficient estimates for alternative dataset versions and calibration periods

Table F2 Linear regression model performance metrics for alternative dataset versions and calibration periods

Figure F1 Comparison of linear regression model fits using previous and current periods of record

Figure F2 Comparison of seasonal TP load and concentration correlations using previous and current periods of record

Table F3 Correlation coefficients of seasonal TP loads and concentrations using previous and current periods

Table F1: Linear regression model coefficient estimates for alternative dataset versions and calibration periods

Dataset	Calibration Period ¹	Term	Estimate	Std. Error	p Value
Walker and Kann (2020) ²	PWY 1994-2010	Intercept	-8,190	3,040	0.0183
		L _{in} [t]	0.656	0.196	0.0053
		L _{in} [t-1]	0.778	0.2	0.0019
		Year	4.05	1.51	0.0186
Current Study	PWY 1994-2010	Intercept	-8,476	2,722	0.0082
		L _{in} [t]	0.642	0.177	0.0031
		L _{in} [t-1]	0.706	0.180	0.0018
		Year	4.199	1.352	0.0083
Current Study	PWY 1994-2018	Intercept	-4,565	1,793	0.0188
		L _{in} [t]	0.584	0.169	0.0023
		L _{in} [t-1]	0.652	0.169	0.0009
		Year	2.253	0.885	0.0188

Table F2: Linear regression model performance metrics for alternative dataset versions and calibration periods

Dataset	Calibration Period ¹	# Years	Adj. R ²	RMSE	Resid. Std. Err.
Walker and Kann (2020) ²	PWY 1994-2010	17	0.67	23	26.3
Current	PWY 1994-2010	17	0.69	29.9	24.7
Current	PWY 1994-2018	25	0.58	24.6	26.8

¹ PWY = Phosphorus Water Year (May 1 - Apr 30; e.g., PWY 2010 = May 1, 2009 - April 30, 2010)

² Walker and Kann (2020) used the previous mass balance dataset from Walker et al. (2012)

Figure F1: Comparison of linear regression model fits using previous and current periods of record

Description: This figure compares the model predictions based on calibrations to the previous period of record (PWY 1994-2010 as analyzed in Walker and Kann, 2020) and the current period of record (PWY 1994-2018). The periods of record both start in PWY 1994 (May 1, 1993 - April 30, 1994) since the full dataset begins on Oct 1, 1991 (start of WY 1992), but the first Phosphorus WY (PWY) does not begin until May 1, 1992 (PWY 1993). Furthermore, because the model includes a 1-year lag term, the first year with complete set of input variables is PWY 1994, which uses PWY 1993 for the 1-year lag term.

The two model versions are compared using

- a) timeseries of annual predict and observed outflow TP load and
- b) scatterplot between observed and predicted annual outflows (diagonal lines are 1:1 lines of equality)

This figures shows that using the original period (PWY 1992-2010) resulted in over-prediction of the following 8 years (PWY 2011-2018). The model fitted to the full period (PWY 1992-2018) better fit the later years due to a reduction in the estimated coefficient for the year (i.e., trend) term (see Table F1).

Figure F2: Comparison of seasonal TP load and concentration correlations using previous and current periods of record

Description: This figure compares the correlations between seasonal TP loads and concentrations based on the previous period of record (PWY 1993-2010 as analyzed in Walker and Kann, 2020) and the current period of record (PWY 1993-2018). The periods of record both start in PWY 1993 (May 1, 1992 - April 30, 1993) since the full dataset begins on Oct 1, 1991 (start of WY 1992), but the first Phosphorus WY (PWY) does not begin until May 1, 1992 (PWY 1993).

Each panel shows the correlation and fitted linear regression models between a pair of seasonal TP loads or concentrations. The individual years are colored by period. The two models are fit using the two alternative periods.

This figures shows that the additional 8 years of data (PWY 2011-2018) generally fall within the range of variability observed during the previous period. They also show that these last 8 years had relatively low loads and net retention rates (most red points clustered in a single quadrant of each panel).

Table F3: Correlation coefficients of seasonal TP loads and concentrations using previous and current periods

Description: Correlation coefficient for each pairwise comparison shown in Figure F2 using the previous and current periods of record. All correlations are statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) based on the cor.test() function in R (R Core Team, 2021).

Panel	X Variable	Y Variable	Periods (PWY)	
			1993-2010	1993-2018
a	Annual Net Inflow TP Load	Winter Net Inflow TP Load	0.87	0.86
b	Winter Net Inflow TP Load	Winter Net Retention TP Load	0.76	0.77
c	Prev. Winter Net Retention TP Load	Summer Net Retention TP Load	-0.70	-0.70
d	Summer Net Retention TP Load	Summer Outflow TP Load	-0.78	-0.77
e	Summer Outflow TP Load	Annual Outflow TP Load	0.90	0.89
f	Summer Outflow TP Load	Summer Outflow TP Conc	0.79	0.76
g	Summer Outflow TP Conc	Annual Outflow TP Conc	0.87	0.88

Appendix G

Trends in Flow, Load, and Concentrations of Mass Balance Terms

Figure G1 Summary of trend test results over previous period of record, WY 1992–2010

Figure G2 Diagnostic plots of seasonal Kendall, Mann-Kendall, and linear regression trends

Table G1 Tabulated trend test results over period of record (WY 1992-2018)

Figure G1: Summary of trend test results over previous period of record, WY 1992–2010

Description: Results of seasonal Kendall trend tests for each term and parameter over the previous period of record, WY 1992–2010. This figure was generated for evaluating changes to the results from Walker et al. (2012) due to revisions in the dataset (e.g., updated bathymetry) and trend methodology (e.g., using the log-transform values instead of untransformed values). Results are generally consistent with the previous report.

Note: All tests computed using seasonal Kendall test with $\log_{10}$ -transform values except for evaporation flows and net retention loads. For evaporation, the slope was estimated from Mann-Kendall test of untransformed annual values and divided by long-term mean annual evaporation to convert to relative slope (%/yr). For net retention, the slope was estimated from seasonal Kendall test of untransformed monthly values and the relative slope (%/yr) was computed by dividing slope in mton/yr by the long-term mean of total external inflow loads.

Figure G2: Diagnostic plots of seasonal Kendall, Mann-Kendall, and linear regression trends

Description: Diagnostic plots of monthly, seasonal and annual trend tests in flow, loads, and concentrations of each mass balance term

Label	Description
Sevenmile@Dike	Sevenmile Canal at Dike Road
Wood@Weed	Wood River at Weed Road
Wood@Dike - Wood@Weed	Wood River between Weed and Dike Roads
Wood@Dike	Wood River at Dike Road
Sprague	Sprague River
Williamson - Sprague	Williamson River downstream of Sprague River
Williamson	Williamson River
Total Gauged Trib. Inflows	Sevenmile@Dike + Wood@Dike + Williamson
ALR Pumped	Agency Lake Ranch
WRDP Pumped	Williamson River Delta Preserve
Ungauged Pumped	Other agricultural areas
Total Pumped Inflows	ALR + WRDP + Ungauged Pumped Areas
Ungauged Inflows	Drainage areas not included in Total Gauged Trib. Inflows or Total Pumped Inflows
Total External Inflows	Total Gauged Trib. Inflows + Total Pumped Inflows + Ungauged Inflows
Precipitation	
Evaporation	
Net Inflow	Total External Inflows + Precipitation - Evaporation
Lake Outflow	
Net Retention	Net Inflow - Lake Outflow - Change in Storage
Lake Mean Storage	
Anthropogenic Sources	
Background Sources	

Panels:	Description
A	Monthly timeseries with trendline showing result of seasonal Kendall test
B	Annual timeseries with trendlines showing results of linear regression and Mann Kendall tests
C	Monthly timeseries with trendline showing result of Mann Kendall test for each individual month
D	Bar chart showing trend slope and significance of each month, 3-month season, and 6-month season based on seasonal Kendall test. "All Months" includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Oct-Sep (SK)</i> Seasonal Kendall Test using all months <i>Annual (MK)</i> Mann Kendall test using annual values <i>Annual (LR)</i> Linear regression test using annual values
E	Page labels, slope and p-value of seasonal Kendall test using all months (Oct-Sep)

Sevenmile | Flow

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Sevenmile
 Variable: Flow
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.30 %/yr	0.0021
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.68 %/yr	0.5878

Sevenmile | Total Phosphorus Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Sevenmile
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-1.19 %/yr	0.0049
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.16 %/yr	0.3813

Sevenmile | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Term: Sevenmile
Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.18 %/yr	0.2978
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.12 %/yr	0.7075

Sevenmile | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Sevenmile
 Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	–2.00 %/yr	0.0015
Mann Kendall (Annual)	–1.30 %/yr	0.2603

Sevensmile | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Sevensmile
 Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.73 %/yr	0.0153
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.25 %/yr	0.5317

Wood@Weed | Flow

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Direction (Significance)

- █ Increase ($p < 0.05$)
- █ Increase ($p < 0.1$)
- █ No Trend ($p \geq 0.1$)
- █ Decrease ($p < 0.1$)
- █ Decrease ($p < 0.05$)

Trend Slopes

Term: Wood@Weed
 Variable: Flow
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.87 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	1.08 %/yr	0.0500

Wood@Weed | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Wood@Weed
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	1.00 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	0.94 %/yr	0.0666

Wood@Weed | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Wood@Weed
Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

	Method	Slope	p-value
	Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.18 %/yr	0.0038
	Mann Kendall (Annual)	0.19 %/yr	0.2266

Wood@Weed | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Direction (Significance)

- Increase ($p < 0.05$)
- Increase ($p < 0.1$)
- No Trend ($p \geq 0.1$)
- Decrease ($p < 0.1$)
- Decrease ($p < 0.05$)

Trend Slopes

Term: Wood@Weed
 Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.03 %/yr	0.9090
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.29 %/yr	0.5594

Wood@Weed | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Wood@Weed
 Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.74 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.28 %/yr	< 0.0001

Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed | Flow

Term: Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed

Variable: Flow

Transform: log₁₀

Period: WY1992–2018

	Method	Slope	p-value
	Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	1.29 %/yr	0.0016
	Mann Kendall (Annual)	1.55 %/yr	0.1689

Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed

Variable: Total Phosphorus Load

Transform: log₁₀

Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	0.33 %/yr	0.1999
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.24 %/yr	0.7704

Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed

Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-1.09 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.53 %/yr	0.1131

Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed

Variable: Total Nitrogen Load

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-1.67 %/yr	0.0037
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-2.67 %/yr	0.0606

Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Wood@Dike – Wood@Weed

Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-3.48 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-3.37 %/yr	0.0005

Wood@Dike | Flow

Term: Wood@Dike
 Variable: Flow
 Transform: log₁₀
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.84 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	0.75 %/yr	0.0799

Wood@Dike | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Wood@Dike
 Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.74 %/yr	0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	0.33 %/yr	0.3170

Wood@Dike | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Wood@Dike

Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.20 %/yr	0.0289
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.32 %/yr	0.1821

Wood@Dike | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Direction (Significance)

- Increase ($p < 0.05$)
- Increase ($p < 0.1$)
- No Trend ($p \geq 0.1$)
- Decrease ($p < 0.1$)
- Decrease ($p < 0.05$)

Trend Slopes

Term: Wood@Dike
 Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-0.66 %/yr	0.0256
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.48 %/yr	0.0799

Wood@Dike | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Wood@Dike
 Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.70 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.82 %/yr	0.0004

Sprague | Flow

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Sprague
 Variable: Flow
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-0.76 %/yr	0.0174
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.38 %/yr	0.2783

Sprague | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Sprague

Variable: Total Phosphorus Load

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.28 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-2.23 %/yr	0.2430

Sprague | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Sprague
 Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.57 %/yr	0.0006
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.76 %/yr	0.0411

Sprague | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Sprague
 Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.57 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-2.51 %/yr	0.2110

Sprague | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Sprague
 Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.57 %/yr	0.0226
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.15 %/yr	0.8349

Williamson – Sprague | Flow

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Williamson – Sprague

Variable: Flow

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	0.47 %/yr	0.0003
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.14 %/yr	0.7704

Williamson – Sprague | Total Phosphorus Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Williamson – Sprague

Variable: Total Phosphorus Load

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	–0.19 %/yr	0.1404
Mann Kendall (Annual)	–0.40 %/yr	0.2973

Williamson – Sprague | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Williamson – Sprague
 Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-0.48 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.42 %/yr	0.1445

Williamson – Sprague | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Williamson – Sprague

Variable: Total Nitrogen Load

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-1.51 %/yr	0.0039
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-3.41 %/yr	0.0196

Williamson – Sprague | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Term: Williamson – Sprague
Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-1.80 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-3.27 %/yr	0.0124

Williamson | Flow

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Direction (Significance)

- Increase ($p < 0.05$)
- Increase ($p < 0.1$)
- No Trend ($p \geq 0.1$)
- Decrease ($p < 0.1$)
- Decrease ($p < 0.05$)

Trend Slopes

Term: Williamson
Variable: Flow
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	–0.01 %/yr	0.9568
Mann Kendall (Annual)	–0.97 %/yr	0.2973

Williamson | Total Phosphorus Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Williamson
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.49 %/yr	0.0030
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.59 %/yr	0.2266

Williamson | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Williamson
 Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-0.28 %/yr	0.0020
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.53 %/yr	0.0271

Williamson | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Williamson
 Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.35 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-3.91 %/yr	0.0551

Williamson | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Williamson
 Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.25 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.79 %/yr	0.0156

Total Gauged Trib. Inflows | Flow

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Direction (Significance)

- Increase ($p < 0.05$)
- Increase ($p < 0.1$)
- No Trend ($p \geq 0.1$)
- Decrease ($p < 0.1$)
- Decrease ($p < 0.05$)

Trend Slopes

Term: Total Gauged Trib. Inflows

Variable: Flow

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992-2018

	Method	Slope	p-value
	Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.09 %/yr	0.6780
	Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.50 %/yr	0.5047

Total Gauged Trib. Inflows | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Total Gauged Trib. Inflows
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.29 %/yr	0.1372
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.82 %/yr	0.2603

Total Gauged Trib. Inflows | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Total Gauged Trib. Inflows

Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.24 %/yr	0.0033
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.37 %/yr	0.0606

Total Gauged Trib. Inflows | Total Nitrogen Load

Term: Total Gauged Trib. Inflows
Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-2.06 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-3.17 %/yr	0.0666

Total Gauged Trib. Inflows | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Term: Total Gauged Trib. Inflows
Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.86 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-2.17 %/yr	0.0035

Total Pumped Inflows | Flow

Term: Total Pumped Inflows
Variable: Flow
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-2.34 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-3.15 %/yr	0.0001

Total Pumped Inflows | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Total Pumped Inflows
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-3.85 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-5.21 %/yr	0.0007

Total Pumped Inflows | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Term: Total Pumped Inflows
Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.50 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.56 %/yr	0.0111

Total Pumped Inflows | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Total Pumped Inflows

Variable: Total Nitrogen Load

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-2.14 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-2.26 %/yr	0.0139

Total Pumped Inflows | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Total Pumped Inflows

Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.21 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	0.94 %/yr	0.0038

Ungauged Inflows | Flow

Term: Ungauged Inflows
Variable: Flow
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.78 %/yr	0.0251
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.67 %/yr	0.0454

Ungauged Inflows | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Ungauged Inflows
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log₁₀
Period: WY1992–2018

	<i>Method</i>	<i>Slope</i>	<i>p-value</i>
	Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	–0.78 %/yr	0.0251
	Mann Kendall (Annual)	–1.67 %/yr	0.0454

Ungauged Inflows | Total Nitrogen Load

Term: Ungauged Inflows

Variable: Total Nitrogen Load

Transform: log₁₀

Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.78 %/yr	0.0251
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.67 %/yr	0.0454

Total External Inflows | Flow

Term: Total External Inflows
Variable: Flow
Transform: log₁₀
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.22 %/yr	0.2604
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.67 %/yr	0.3376

Total External Inflows | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Total External Inflows
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.66 %/yr	0.0005
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.60 %/yr	0.0606

Total External Inflows | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Term: Total External Inflows
Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.55 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.73 %/yr	0.0005

Total External Inflows | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Total External Inflows

Variable: Total Nitrogen Load

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.93 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-2.95 %/yr	0.0196

Total External Inflows | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Term: Total External Inflows
Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.76 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.49 %/yr	0.0018

Precipitation | Flow

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

- Trend Direction (Significance)**
- Increase ($p < 0.05$)
 - Increase ($p < 0.1$)
 - No Trend ($p \geq 0.1$)
 - Decrease ($p < 0.1$)
 - Decrease ($p < 0.05$)

Trend Slopes

Term: Precipitation
 Variable: Flow
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-0.61 %/yr	0.3205
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.55 %/yr	0.4283

Precipitation | Total Phosphorus Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Precipitation
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.07 %/yr	0.7589
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.18 %/yr	0.8025

Precipitation | Total Nitrogen Load

Term: Precipitation
Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.07 %/yr	0.7589
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.18 %/yr	0.8025

Evaporation | Flow

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Evaporation
 Variable: Flow
 Transform: none
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.00 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	0.70 %/yr	0.0007

Net Inflow | Flow

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Net Inflow
Variable: Flow
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	–0.50 %/yr	0.0863
Mann Kendall (Annual)	–0.98 %/yr	0.2783

Net Inflow | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Net Inflow
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.62 %/yr	0.0010
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.53 %/yr	0.0730

Net Inflow | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Net Inflow

Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.27 %/yr	0.0057
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.26 %/yr	0.1229

Net Inflow | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Net Inflow
 Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
 Transform: log10
 Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.61 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-2.72 %/yr	0.0175

Net Inflow | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Net Inflow
Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.15 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.04 %/yr	0.0005

Lake Outflow | Flow

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Lake Outflow
Variable: Flow
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-0.44 %/yr	0.0519
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.76 %/yr	0.3376

Lake Outflow | Total Phosphorus Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Direction (Significance)

- █ Increase ($p < 0.05$)
- █ Increase ($p < 0.1$)
- █ No Trend ($p \geq 0.1$)
- █ Decrease ($p < 0.1$)
- █ Decrease ($p < 0.05$)

Trend Slopes

Term: Lake Outflow
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.55 %/yr	0.2264
Mann Kendall (Annual)	0.27 %/yr	0.7075

Lake Outflow | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Lake Outflow
Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.12 %/yr	0.7225
Mann Kendall (Annual)	0.99 %/yr	0.0500

Lake Outflow | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Lake Outflow
Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.90 %/yr	0.0098
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.10 %/yr	0.1821

Lake Outflow | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Term: Lake Outflow
Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.16 %/yr	0.4889
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.02 %/yr	0.9335

Net Retention | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Net Retention
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: none
Period: WY1992–2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	-2.13 %/yr	0.0549
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-1.07 %/yr	0.1334

Note: Net retention computed using untransformed values, percent slope computed relative to long-term mean total external inflow load

Net Retention | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct–Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Net Retention

Variable: Total Nitrogen Load

Transform: none

Period: WY1992–2018

	<i>Method</i>	<i>Slope</i>	<i>p-value</i>
	Seasonal Kendall (Oct–Sep)	1.00 %/yr	0.7958
	Mann Kendall (Annual)	1.78 %/yr	0.5878

Note: Net retention computed using untransformed values, percent slope computed relative to long-term mean total external inflow load

Lake Mean Storage | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Term: Lake Mean Storage
Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	0.01 %/yr	0.9760
Mann Kendall (Annual)	0.17 %/yr	0.6465

Lake Mean Storage | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Term: Lake Mean Storage
Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.04 %/yr	0.8804
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.24 %/yr	0.7075

Background Inflows | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Background Inflows
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.22 %/yr	0.2604
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.67 %/yr	0.3376

Background Inflows | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Background Inflows
Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-0.22 %/yr	0.2604
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-0.67 %/yr	0.3376

Anthropogenic Inflows | Total Phosphorus Load

Term: Anthropogenic Inflows
Variable: Total Phosphorus Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-2.01 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-3.07 %/yr	0.0110

Anthropogenic Inflows | Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Anthropogenic Inflows

Variable: Total Phosphorus FWM Conc

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-1.95 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-2.02 %/yr	0.0005

Anthropogenic Inflows | Total Nitrogen Load

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Direction (Significance)

- Increase ($p < 0.05$)
- Increase ($p < 0.1$)
- No Trend ($p \geq 0.1$)
- Decrease ($p < 0.1$)
- Decrease ($p < 0.05$)

Trend Slopes

Term: Anthropogenic Inflows
Variable: Total Nitrogen Load
Transform: log10
Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-3.88 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-3.55 %/yr	0.0067

Anthropogenic Inflows | Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Monthly Timeseries

Trendline = Seasonal Kendall Test (Oct-Sep)

Annual Timeseries

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test (solid), Linear Regression (dashed)

Annual Timeseries by Month

Trendlines = Mann Kendall Test by Month

Trend Slopes

Term: Anthropogenic Inflows

Variable: Total Nitrogen FWM Conc

Transform: log10

Period: WY1992-2018

Method	Slope	p-value
Seasonal Kendall (Oct-Sep)	-3.22 %/yr	< 0.0001
Mann Kendall (Annual)	-2.22 %/yr	0.0018

Table G1: Tabulated trend test results over period of record (WY 1992-2018)

Description: Estimated trend slopes and p-values of for each mass balance term over varying months and seasons

Terms:	Label	Description
	Sevenmile@Dike	Sevenmile Canal at Dike Road
	Wood@Weed	Wood River at Weed Road
	Wood@Dike - Wood@Weed	Wood River between Weed and Dike Roads
	Wood@Dike	Wood River at Dike Road
	Sprague	Sprague River
	Williamson - Sprague	Williamson River downstream of Sprague River
	Williamson	Williamson River
	Total Gauged Trib. Inflows	Sevenmile@Dike + Wood@Dike + Williamson
	ALR Pumped	Agency Lake Ranch
	WRDP Pumped	Williamson River Delta Preserve
	Ungauged Pumped	Other agricultural areas
	Total Pumped Inflows	ALR + WRDP + Ungauged Pumped Areas
	Ungauged Inflows	Drainage areas not included in Total Gauged Trib. Inflows or Total Pumped Inflows
	Total External Inflows	Total Gauged Trib. Inflows + Total Pumped Inflows + Ungauged Inflows
	Precipitation	
	Evaporation	
	Net Inflow	Total External Inflows + Precipitation - Evaporation
	Lake Outflow	
	Net Retention	Net Inflow - Lake Outflow - Change in Storage
	Lake Mean Storage	
	Anthropogenic Sources	
	Background Sources	

Seasons:	Monthly	
		Oct
		Nov
		Dec
		Jan
		Feb
		Mar
		Apr
		May
		Jun
		Jul
		Aug
		Sep
	3-Month Seasons	Oct-Dec Jan-Mar Apr-Jun Jul-Sep
	6-Month Seasons	Oct-Mar Apr-Sep
	12-Month/Annual	Oct-Sep Annual

Tests:		
MK	Mann-Kendall Test	
SK	Seasonal Kendall Test	
LR	Linear Regression	

Color Key:	
	Increasing Trend (p < 0.05)
	Increasing Trend (p < 0.1)
	No Trend (p >= 0.1)
	Decreasing Trend (p < 0.1)
	Decreasing Trend (p < 0.05)

Term	Season	Test	Flow		TP Load		TP Concentration		TN Load		TN Concentration	
			Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value
Sevenmile	Oct	MK	-1.86	0.0500	-1.31	0.1962	0.82	0.0371	-1.53	0.3590	0.40	0.7075
	Nov	MK	-1.65	0.0874	-1.61	0.0730	0.39	0.4785	-2.36	0.2110	-0.08	1.0000
	Dec	MK	-1.38	0.3376	-1.55	0.2783	-0.61	0.1821	-3.09	0.1821	-1.84	0.2110
	Jan	MK	0.05	1.0000	-0.33	0.8349	-0.09	0.9005	0.22	0.9335	-0.80	0.4283
	Feb	MK	2.45	0.2783	3.02	0.2973	0.63	0.2973	2.40	0.5317	-0.52	0.7387
	Mar	MK	1.46	0.3590	2.15	0.4044	0.31	0.7075	1.45	0.4044	-0.58	0.5878
	Apr	MK	1.55	0.4530	2.34	0.1039	0.73	0.5594	2.74	0.1689	0.88	0.3590
	May	MK	-2.15	0.2973	-0.69	0.6465	1.85	0.1131	0.30	0.9005	2.57	0.0218
	Jun	MK	-2.44	0.1131	-1.95	0.2266	0.36	0.6465	-3.08	0.1563	-0.50	0.5317
	Jul	MK	-3.91	0.0454	-5.62	0.0156	-0.56	0.2430	-6.37	0.0023	-2.30	0.0031
	Aug	MK	-4.14	0.0606	-5.33	0.0052	-1.03	0.1445	-7.77	0.0006	-3.23	0.0003
	Sep	MK	-2.72	0.0271	-2.81	0.0606	0.30	0.4283	-4.07	0.0086	-1.05	0.0730
	Oct-Dec	SK	-1.65	0.0070	-1.48	0.0150	0.26	0.3995	-2.20	0.0407	-0.41	0.6132
	Jan-Mar	SK	1.29	0.2382	1.49	0.3356	0.21	0.4555	1.01	0.3603	-0.61	0.3237
	Apr-Jun	SK	-0.96	0.2787	-0.03	0.9808	0.91	0.1234	0.06	0.9616	0.89	0.1356
	Jul-Sep	SK	-3.61	0.0004	-4.46	0.0000	-0.35	0.2895	-5.98	0.0000	-2.10	0.0000
	Oct-Mar	SK	-0.67	0.2874	-0.44	0.3031	0.23	0.2577	-0.65	0.4287	-0.52	0.2874
Apr-Sep	SK	-2.11	0.0011	-2.17	0.0033	0.12	0.7400	-3.14	0.0002	-0.95	0.0184	
Oct-Sep	SK	-1.30	0.0021	-1.19	0.0049	0.18	0.2978	-2.00	0.0015	-0.73	0.0153	
Annual	MK	-0.68	0.5878	-1.16	0.3813	-0.12	0.7075	-1.30	0.2603	-0.25	0.5317	
Annual	LR	-0.54	0.5397	-0.66	0.5345	-0.12	0.7847	-0.97	0.3910	-0.44	0.3599	
Wood@Weed	Oct	MK	0.81	0.2110	0.98	0.0666	0.31	0.1445	0.17	0.9005	-0.35	0.0196
	Nov	MK	0.72	0.1821	0.57	0.1821	0.29	0.4044	0.42	0.6465	-0.11	0.6168
	Dec	MK	0.78	0.0551	0.88	0.0271	0.31	0.1962	0.61	0.4044	-0.31	0.2430
	Jan	MK	0.59	0.1821	0.53	0.2973	0.02	1.0000	0.15	0.8675	-0.31	0.5047
	Feb	MK	0.72	0.0411	0.63	0.1563	0.25	0.2430	0.31	0.7387	-0.34	0.2973
	Mar	MK	0.87	0.0218	0.94	0.0335	0.47	0.0954	-0.27	0.9335	-0.52	0.3376
	Apr	MK	0.56	0.4785	0.90	0.1821	0.42	0.0139	-0.44	0.6168	-0.74	0.0666
	May	MK	0.70	0.4530	1.09	0.3376	0.42	0.0302	-0.30	0.7704	-0.65	0.0730
	Jun	MK	1.47	0.3376	1.73	0.1962	0.20	0.3170	0.14	0.9335	-1.54	0.0005
	Jul	MK	2.37	0.0454	2.04	0.0730	-0.19	0.4044	-1.33	0.4044	-1.91	0.0001
	Aug	MK	2.79	0.0124	2.47	0.0335	-0.45	0.0606	-0.76	0.6465	-1.47	0.0000
	Sep	MK	1.12	0.1229	1.12	0.0606	0.07	0.5878	-0.22	0.8025	-0.76	0.0010
	Oct-Dec	SK	0.77	0.0087	0.88	0.0018	0.31	0.0362	0.38	0.3995	-0.27	0.0195
	Jan-Mar	SK	0.72	0.0010	0.73	0.0075	0.25	0.0967	0.12	0.8098	-0.41	0.1177
	Apr-Jun	SK	0.72	0.1555	1.17	0.0362	0.38	0.0011	-0.25	0.6824	-1.04	0.0000
	Jul-Sep	SK	1.91	0.0004	1.73	0.0008	-0.18	0.2107	-0.59	0.3603	-1.40	0.0000
	Oct-Mar	SK	0.75	0.0000	0.79	0.0000	0.27	0.0077	0.28	0.4386	-0.31	0.0057
Apr-Sep	SK	1.21	0.0005	1.40	0.0001	0.11	0.1552	-0.43	0.3448	-1.17	0.0000	
Oct-Sep	SK	0.87	0.0000	1.00	0.0000	0.18	0.0038	-0.03	0.9090	-0.74	0.0000	
Annual	MK	1.08	0.0500	0.94	0.0666	0.19	0.2266	-0.29	0.5594	-1.28	0.0000	
Annual	LR	0.76	0.0861	0.79	0.0540	0.04	0.8121	-0.64	0.2068	-1.39	0.0000	

Term	Season	Test	Flow		TP Load		TP Concentration		TN Load		TN Concentration	
			Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value
Wood@Dike - Wood@Weed	Oct	MK	1.49	0.2110	1.20	0.1689	-0.63	0.4044	1.25	0.7704	-1.75	0.2603
	Nov	MK	1.80	0.2603	0.59	0.4530	-0.27	0.6593	-1.28	0.5317	-2.65	0.0707
	Dec	MK	0.20	0.8349	-1.11	0.4283	-1.02	0.3546	-3.26	0.1334	-1.88	0.3780
	Jan	MK	1.12	0.5317	-0.44	0.8025	-1.74	0.1229	-3.43	0.1229	-4.71	0.0048
	Feb	MK	2.49	0.1563	1.34	0.1821	-2.09	0.1718	-0.91	0.6465	-5.58	0.0072
	Mar	MK	2.55	0.0799	1.21	0.2783	-1.58	0.1229	-0.59	0.7387	-3.19	0.0195
	Apr	MK	-0.12	0.8675	-1.03	0.2973	-0.39	0.6593	-0.34	0.8675	-0.73	0.4982
	May	MK	2.21	0.1689	0.84	0.5878	-1.77	0.2704	1.48	0.6465	-1.52	0.5085
	Jun	MK	1.22	0.5047	0.04	1.0000	-1.16	0.2430	-0.62	0.8349	-1.43	0.3813
	Jul	MK	1.38	0.2973	0.03	0.9667	-1.37	0.1131	-2.59	0.1689	-5.10	0.0052
	Aug	MK	1.42	0.2783	0.80	0.2266	-1.12	0.1962	-3.66	0.0454	-5.60	0.0005
	Sep	MK	0.44	0.7387	0.05	0.9335	-1.07	0.0156	-4.48	0.0139	-5.47	0.0003
	Oct-Dec	SK	1.10	0.1294	0.42	0.4411	-0.61	0.1942	-1.15	0.2895	-2.30	0.0263
	Jan-Mar	SK	1.90	0.0268	0.70	0.2107	-1.74	0.0094	-1.60	0.1700	-4.49	0.0000
	Apr-Jun	SK	1.21	0.2787	-0.12	0.7912	-0.95	0.1101	0.10	0.9808	-1.31	0.1906
	Jul-Sep	SK	0.92	0.1487	0.33	0.4270	-1.18	0.0021	-3.58	0.0007	-5.47	0.0000
	Oct-Mar	SK	1.52	0.0081	0.59	0.1503	-1.11	0.0059	-1.41	0.0840	-3.30	0.0000
	Apr-Sep	SK	1.00	0.0725	0.11	0.7144	-1.08	0.0009	-1.96	0.0176	-3.63	0.0000
	Oct-Sep	SK	1.29	0.0016	0.33	0.1999	-1.09	0.0000	-1.67	0.0037	-3.48	0.0000
	Annual	MK	1.55	0.1689	-0.24	0.7704	-1.53	0.1131	-2.67	0.0606	-3.37	0.0005
Annual	LR	2.24	0.0271	0.49	0.5208	-1.71	0.0101	-1.84	0.1321	-3.99	0.0003	
Wood@Dike	Oct	MK	0.70	0.1131	1.16	0.0454	-0.01	1.0000	0.58	0.3590	-0.49	0.1445
	Nov	MK	0.73	0.2266	0.90	0.2110	0.14	0.4044	-0.24	0.7075	-0.56	0.1962
	Dec	MK	0.36	0.4283	0.67	0.1039	-0.22	0.5878	-0.60	0.4044	-1.43	0.0454
	Jan	MK	0.41	0.4044	0.04	0.9667	-0.41	0.2973	-1.62	0.0666	-2.05	0.0046
	Feb	MK	0.71	0.0500	0.98	0.1563	-0.04	0.9335	-0.04	0.9005	-1.66	0.0606
	Mar	MK	1.21	0.0067	1.00	0.1039	-0.09	0.8349	-0.37	0.8349	-1.17	0.1563
	Apr	MK	0.40	0.5878	-0.07	0.9005	0.06	0.8025	-0.95	0.5594	-1.05	0.3813
	May	MK	0.48	0.5594	0.81	0.3590	-0.07	0.8675	0.85	0.6465	-0.27	0.7704
	Jun	MK	1.08	0.2603	0.93	0.4044	-0.26	0.4785	-0.12	0.9667	-1.82	0.0371
	Jul	MK	2.11	0.0271	0.76	0.3376	-0.67	0.0454	-1.54	0.1821	-3.08	0.0006
	Aug	MK	2.12	0.0110	1.52	0.0371	-0.50	0.0500	-1.43	0.1039	-3.10	0.0001
	Sep	MK	0.57	0.5317	0.32	0.6168	-0.34	0.0730	-2.12	0.0454	-2.65	0.0000
	Oct-Dec	SK	0.57	0.0362	0.90	0.0045	0.02	0.8852	-0.09	0.8662	-0.79	0.0056
	Jan-Mar	SK	0.83	0.0014	0.65	0.0710	-0.17	0.4270	-0.81	0.2020	-1.66	0.0004
	Apr-Jun	SK	0.61	0.1855	0.53	0.3478	-0.09	0.7180	-0.12	0.9233	-1.13	0.0572
	Jul-Sep	SK	1.46	0.0018	0.76	0.0384	-0.49	0.0008	-1.63	0.0039	-2.89	0.0000
	Oct-Mar	SK	0.68	0.0002	0.79	0.0010	-0.07	0.6519	-0.36	0.3031	-1.12	0.0000
	Apr-Sep	SK	1.03	0.0016	0.68	0.0327	-0.35	0.0085	-0.99	0.0341	-2.33	0.0000
	Oct-Sep	SK	0.84	0.0000	0.74	0.0001	-0.20	0.0289	-0.66	0.0256	-1.70	0.0000
	Annual	MK	0.75	0.0799	0.33	0.3170	-0.32	0.1821	-1.48	0.0799	-1.82	0.0004
Annual	LR	1.16	0.0120	0.65	0.1354	-0.51	0.0517	-1.10	0.1140	-2.23	0.0001	

Term	Season	Test	Flow		TP Load		TP Concentration		TN Load		TN Concentration	
			Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value
Sprague	Oct	MK	-0.72	0.1689	-0.87	0.0799	-0.31	0.4283	-1.35	0.0666	-0.41	0.4785
	Nov	MK	-0.79	0.0666	-1.43	0.0954	-0.72	0.1039	-1.91	0.0097	-1.13	0.0335
	Dec	MK	-0.17	0.8349	-0.68	0.7704	-0.21	0.5317	-0.66	0.7075	-0.39	0.6168
	Jan	MK	-1.36	0.4044	-2.52	0.1689	-1.42	0.2783	-1.94	0.5317	-0.98	0.5047
	Feb	MK	-0.28	0.8025	-1.06	0.5047	-0.79	0.2266	-1.22	0.7704	-0.78	0.5878
	Mar	MK	-1.53	0.5317	-0.47	0.7704	0.00	1.0000	-0.28	0.9005	0.51	0.5317
	Apr	MK	-1.92	0.3813	-2.13	0.2973	-0.46	0.3813	-1.51	0.5594	0.42	0.5047
	May	MK	-2.58	0.2430	-1.78	0.4044	-0.42	0.4785	-2.11	0.4283	0.63	0.2603
	Jun	MK	-2.34	0.2783	-2.34	0.2973	-0.43	0.5047	-0.86	0.5594	-0.07	0.9667
	Jul	MK	-1.01	0.6168	-2.18	0.0335	-1.15	0.1962	-1.35	0.0371	-0.66	0.4785
	Aug	MK	0.45	0.5878	-0.75	0.2110	-0.80	0.2266	-1.11	0.0271	-1.55	0.0730
	Sep	MK	0.14	0.9005	-1.35	0.1039	-0.95	0.1131	-2.47	0.0001	-1.95	0.0018
	Oct-Dec	SK	-0.64	0.0457	-0.96	0.0303	-0.44	0.0749	-1.47	0.0052	-0.76	0.0512
	Jan-Mar	SK	-0.95	0.3120	-1.31	0.1700	-0.58	0.1855	-1.33	0.5314	-0.31	0.7361
	Apr-Jun	SK	-2.12	0.0673	-2.06	0.0874	-0.43	0.1855	-1.52	0.2479	0.37	0.3120
	Jul-Sep	SK	0.03	0.9233	-1.28	0.0036	-0.96	0.0172	-1.66	0.0000	-1.50	0.0011
	Oct-Mar	SK	-0.68	0.0327	-1.05	0.0121	-0.49	0.0275	-1.40	0.0153	-0.59	0.1040
Apr-Sep	SK	-0.86	0.2236	-1.50	0.0011	-0.66	0.0085	-1.63	0.0000	-0.54	0.1115	
Oct-Sep	SK	-0.76	0.0174	-1.28	0.0000	-0.57	0.0006	-1.57	0.0000	-0.57	0.0226	
Annual	MK	-1.38	0.2783	-2.23	0.2430	-0.76	0.0411	-2.51	0.2110	-0.15	0.8349	
Annual	LR	-0.98	0.3924	-1.69	0.2303	-0.71	0.0326	-1.14	0.4620	-0.16	0.7606	
Williamson - Sprague	Oct	MK	0.65	0.0031	0.11	0.7075	-0.49	0.0606	0.09	0.9667	-0.06	0.9667
	Nov	MK	0.42	0.0666	-0.17	0.7075	-0.35	0.2266	-0.58	0.4044	-1.20	0.2603
	Dec	MK	0.07	0.8675	-0.36	0.4530	-0.23	0.6168	-6.21	0.0059	-5.32	0.0052
	Jan	MK	-1.49	0.1334	-1.75	0.0196	-0.77	0.0454	-8.32	0.0196	-6.54	0.0244
	Feb	MK	-1.74	0.0666	-0.93	0.5317	0.12	0.8025	-5.29	0.1563	-3.73	0.1334
	Mar	MK	-0.86	0.5594	-1.03	0.1821	0.25	0.6465	-2.40	0.3590	-1.48	0.2783
	Apr	MK	-0.65	0.5317	-0.86	0.3170	-0.17	0.7387	-4.04	0.0302	-2.47	0.0551
	May	MK	-0.16	0.9667	-0.61	0.4283	-0.36	0.4785	-2.95	0.2430	-2.69	0.1689
	Jun	MK	0.87	0.1563	0.81	0.1821	-0.03	0.9335	-2.19	0.4044	-3.38	0.1445
	Jul	MK	1.57	0.0011	0.13	0.8349	-1.07	0.0035	1.82	0.3376	-0.22	0.8349
	Aug	MK	1.12	0.0001	0.20	0.5594	-0.68	0.0011	1.25	0.3590	0.15	0.8675
	Sep	MK	0.91	0.0005	-0.07	0.7387	-0.70	0.0086	0.94	0.5594	0.47	0.9005
	Oct-Dec	SK	0.40	0.0039	-0.11	0.6648	-0.38	0.0362	-1.53	0.0407	-1.80	0.0208
	Jan-Mar	SK	-1.48	0.0222	-1.19	0.0123	-0.23	0.4702	-5.05	0.0065	-3.49	0.0049
	Apr-Jun	SK	0.18	0.6824	-0.08	0.7912	-0.18	0.5003	-3.10	0.0150	-2.69	0.0056
	Jul-Sep	SK	1.08	0.0000	0.05	0.7912	-0.78	0.0000	1.31	0.1487	0.09	0.9616
	Oct-Mar	SK	0.11	0.6767	-0.40	0.0371	-0.34	0.0455	-2.57	0.0007	-2.52	0.0003
Apr-Sep	SK	0.92	0.0000	0.01	1.0000	-0.59	0.0000	-0.52	0.4906	-1.25	0.0555	
Oct-Sep	SK	0.47	0.0003	-0.19	0.1404	-0.48	0.0000	-1.51	0.0039	-1.80	0.0001	
Annual	MK	-0.14	0.7704	-0.40	0.2973	-0.42	0.1445	-3.41	0.0196	-3.27	0.0124	
Annual	LR	0.03	0.9433	-0.53	0.2257	-0.56	0.0636	-2.56	0.1023	-2.59	0.0400	

Term	Season	Test	Flow		TP Load		TP Concentration		TN Load		TN Concentration	
			Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value
Williamson	Oct	MK	0.18	0.4785	-0.24	0.4283	-0.08	0.7387	-0.65	0.2430	-0.86	0.0666
	Nov	MK	-0.01	0.9335	-0.60	0.1563	-0.32	0.3170	-1.75	0.0218	-1.73	0.0076
	Dec	MK	-0.11	0.8675	-0.15	0.7387	-0.26	0.4530	-2.19	0.1039	-1.96	0.0500
	Jan	MK	-0.79	0.3813	-1.99	0.1445	-0.87	0.0551	-3.46	0.1821	-2.28	0.1229
	Feb	MK	-0.88	0.7704	-1.02	0.5317	-0.19	0.7075	-2.58	0.2973	-2.05	0.2973
	Mar	MK	-2.18	0.1445	-1.53	0.5047	0.08	0.8675	-3.43	0.1131	-0.86	0.2430
	Apr	MK	-1.58	0.3376	-1.49	0.2430	-0.34	0.2430	-2.52	0.1821	-0.93	0.1563
	May	MK	-2.04	0.2603	-1.58	0.4283	-0.06	0.8675	-2.46	0.2973	-0.22	0.9335
	Jun	MK	-0.71	0.6465	-0.37	0.7075	0.07	0.9335	-1.45	0.2973	-1.19	0.1563
	Jul	MK	0.72	0.3813	-0.55	0.2603	-0.37	0.1445	-0.45	0.4283	-1.33	0.0454
	Aug	MK	0.92	0.0551	-0.05	0.9667	-0.65	0.0551	0.17	0.8349	-0.83	0.0799
	Sep	MK	0.61	0.0730	-0.31	0.2110	-0.35	0.0874	-1.61	0.0302	-1.76	0.0035
	Oct-Dec	SK	0.06	0.8098	-0.37	0.1356	-0.19	0.2196	-1.35	0.0031	-1.55	0.0002
	Jan-Mar	SK	-1.18	0.1234	-1.49	0.1068	-0.40	0.2196	-3.17	0.0208	-1.53	0.0285
	Apr-Jun	SK	-1.29	0.1356	-1.22	0.1700	-0.11	0.4702	-2.22	0.0457	-0.81	0.0874
	Jul-Sep	SK	0.75	0.0075	-0.26	0.1555	-0.41	0.0031	-0.49	0.1121	-1.26	0.0001
	Oct-Mar	SK	-0.20	0.3625	-0.61	0.0275	-0.25	0.0810	-1.90	0.0002	-1.54	0.0000
	Apr-Sep	SK	0.23	0.4091	-0.40	0.0474	-0.30	0.0090	-0.93	0.0109	-1.09	0.0001
	Oct-Sep	SK	-0.01	0.9568	-0.49	0.0030	-0.28	0.0020	-1.35	0.0000	-1.25	0.0000
Annual	MK	-0.97	0.2973	-1.59	0.2266	-0.53	0.0271	-3.91	0.0551	-1.79	0.0156	
Annual	LR	-0.64	0.4087	-1.18	0.1674	-0.54	0.0119	-1.76	0.2155	-1.13	0.1221	
Total Gauged Trib. Inflows	Oct	MK	0.27	0.5594	0.05	0.9005	-0.03	0.8675	-0.61	0.1962	-1.04	0.0454
	Nov	MK	0.22	0.5594	-0.08	0.8675	-0.07	0.7075	-1.94	0.1563	-1.76	0.0371
	Dec	MK	-0.16	0.8675	-0.29	0.6465	-0.32	0.3590	-2.13	0.1334	-1.71	0.0500
	Jan	MK	-0.02	0.9335	-0.81	0.3376	-0.68	0.1334	-2.77	0.1821	-2.31	0.0500
	Feb	MK	0.00	1.0000	-0.05	0.9667	-0.05	0.9335	-1.67	0.2783	-1.78	0.2110
	Mar	MK	-1.22	0.3376	-0.63	0.5317	0.06	0.8349	-2.57	0.1689	-1.23	0.1563
	Apr	MK	-1.04	0.4283	-0.53	0.6767	0.05	0.9005	-2.44	0.1821	-0.98	0.2430
	May	MK	-1.50	0.4044	-0.75	0.6168	0.27	0.2110	-2.33	0.3376	-0.28	0.7075
	Jun	MK	-0.49	0.7704	-0.60	0.6465	-0.10	0.8349	-1.89	0.4044	-1.83	0.0454
	Jul	MK	0.95	0.2783	-0.45	0.5317	-0.82	0.0007	-2.45	0.0156	-3.36	0.0000
	Aug	MK	1.11	0.0799	-0.03	0.9335	-0.88	0.0003	-2.00	0.0035	-2.72	0.0000
	Sep	MK	0.44	0.5594	-0.45	0.4530	-0.26	0.1445	-2.73	0.0013	-2.60	0.0000
	Oct-Dec	SK	0.15	0.5634	-0.07	0.7727	-0.11	0.3862	-1.17	0.0141	-1.37	0.0004
	Jan-Mar	SK	-0.42	0.5473	-0.63	0.3356	-0.21	0.4270	-2.39	0.0268	-1.68	0.0070
	Apr-Jun	SK	-0.89	0.2579	-0.62	0.4131	0.12	0.5003	-2.31	0.0673	-1.12	0.0384
	Jul-Sep	SK	0.72	0.0457	-0.31	0.3862	-0.66	0.0000	-2.35	0.0000	-2.79	0.0000
	Oct-Mar	SK	-0.01	0.9932	-0.22	0.3715	-0.14	0.2368	-1.67	0.0009	-1.49	0.0000
	Apr-Sep	SK	0.23	0.5457	-0.43	0.2301	-0.35	0.0030	-2.34	0.0000	-2.15	0.0000
	Oct-Sep	SK	0.09	0.6780	-0.29	0.1372	-0.24	0.0033	-2.06	0.0000	-1.86	0.0000
Annual	MK	-0.50	0.5047	-0.82	0.2603	-0.37	0.0606	-3.17	0.0666	-2.17	0.0035	
Annual	LR	-0.16	0.8056	-0.54	0.4494	-0.38	0.0568	-1.63	0.1672	-1.47	0.0170	

Term	Season	Test	Flow		TP Load		TP Concentration		TN Load		TN Concentration	
			Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value
Total Pumped Inflows	Oct	MK	-3.30	0.0076	-5.03	0.0035	-1.44	0.0000	-3.03	0.0067	0.00	0.0095
	Nov	MK	-2.41	0.0035	-2.82	0.0011	-1.08	0.0002	-2.45	0.0023	0.00	0.0000
	Dec	MK	-2.25	0.0040	-2.79	0.0011	-0.98	0.0000	-2.45	0.0018	0.00	0.0035
	Jan	MK	-2.42	0.0009	-3.74	0.0000	-1.66	0.0001	-2.42	0.0006	0.00	0.0385
	Feb	MK	-2.42	0.0009	-4.08	0.0000	-1.66	0.0000	-2.56	0.0005	0.00	0.0858
	Mar	MK	-3.50	0.0009	-5.45	0.0001	-1.74	0.0000	-2.91	0.0006	0.00	0.0155
	Apr	MK	-2.24	0.0500	-3.67	0.0035	-1.52	0.0017	-1.89	0.0244	0.78	0.0146
	May	MK	-1.23	0.2266	-1.79	0.2430	-0.69	0.1279	-0.66	0.5047	0.99	0.0012
	Jun	MK	-0.23	0.4785	-1.24	0.3590	-1.32	0.2838	-0.09	0.7387	1.05	0.0005
	Jul	MK	-2.74	0.0666	-4.23	0.0335	-1.10	0.0040	-2.23	0.0874	0.91	0.0009
	Aug	MK	-3.74	0.0059	-5.57	0.0023	-1.66	0.0001	-3.27	0.0040	0.00	0.0709
	Sep	MK	-3.52	0.0035	-5.21	0.0015	-1.59	0.0000	-3.18	0.0027	0.00	0.1188
	Oct-Dec	SK	-2.70	0.0000	-3.71	0.0000	-1.18	0.0000	-2.56	0.0000	0.00	0.0000
	Jan-Mar	SK	-2.74	0.0000	-4.57	0.0000	-1.71	0.0000	-2.74	0.0000	0.00	0.0003
	Apr-Jun	SK	-1.44	0.0237	-2.89	0.0036	-1.26	0.0009	-1.22	0.0572	0.94	0.0000
	Jul-Sep	SK	-3.37	0.0000	-5.04	0.0000	-1.51	0.0000	-2.89	0.0000	0.20	0.0001
	Oct-Mar	SK	-2.70	0.0000	-4.34	0.0000	-1.53	0.0000	-2.70	0.0000	0.00	0.0000
	Apr-Sep	SK	-2.07	0.0000	-3.65	0.0000	-1.42	0.0000	-1.84	0.0000	0.78	0.0000
Oct-Sep	SK	-2.34	0.0000	-3.85	0.0000	-1.50	0.0000	-2.14	0.0000	0.21	0.0000	
Annual	MK	-3.15	0.0001	-5.21	0.0007	-1.56	0.0111	-2.26	0.0139	0.94	0.0038	
Annual	LR	-3.62	0.0000	-5.38	0.0000	-1.82	0.0290	-2.77	0.0006	0.89	0.0057	
Ungauged Inflows	Oct	MK	-0.68	0.6168	-0.68	0.6168			-0.68	0.6168		
	Nov	MK	0.55	0.7075	0.55	0.7075			0.55	0.7075		
	Dec	MK	-2.14	0.3376	-2.14	0.3376			-2.14	0.3376		
	Jan	MK	-5.74	0.0218	-5.74	0.0218			-5.74	0.0218		
	Feb	MK	-9.62	0.0060	-9.62	0.0060			-9.62	0.0060		
	Mar	MK	-2.40	0.1681	-2.40	0.1681			-2.40	0.1681		
	Apr	MK	-2.86	0.1334	-2.86	0.1334			-2.86	0.1334		
	May	MK	-0.87	0.4044	-0.87	0.4044			-0.87	0.4044		
	Jun	MK	1.24	0.2783	1.24	0.2783			1.24	0.2783		
	Jul	MK	-0.28	0.6465	-0.28	0.6465			-0.28	0.6465		
	Aug	MK	1.54	0.2266	1.54	0.2266			1.54	0.2266		
	Sep	MK	0.40	0.7704	0.40	0.7704			0.40	0.7704		
	Oct-Dec	SK	-0.63	0.5314	-0.63	0.5314			-0.63	0.5314		
	Jan-Mar	SK	-5.61	0.0002	-5.61	0.0002			-5.61	0.0002		
	Apr-Jun	SK	-0.53	0.4702	-0.53	0.4702			-0.53	0.4702		
	Jul-Sep	SK	0.31	0.5473	0.31	0.5473			0.31	0.5473		
	Oct-Mar	SK	-2.23	0.0020	-2.23	0.0020			-2.23	0.0020		
	Apr-Sep	SK	-0.04	0.9389	-0.04	0.9389			-0.04	0.9389		
Oct-Sep	SK	-0.78	0.0251	-0.78	0.0251			-0.78	0.0251			
Annual	MK	-1.67	0.0454	-1.67	0.0454			-1.67	0.0454			
Annual	LR	-1.37	0.0610	-1.37	0.0610			-1.37	0.0610			

Term	Season	Test	Flow		TP Load		TP Concentration		TN Load		TN Concentration	
			Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value
Total External Inflows	Oct	MK	-0.18	0.7704	-0.49	0.3590	-0.28	0.1689	-0.97	0.0271	-1.30	0.0013
	Nov	MK	-0.06	0.9005	-0.22	0.6465	-0.26	0.1445	-1.65	0.1039	-1.83	0.0007
	Dec	MK	-0.17	0.8349	-0.32	0.6767	-0.41	0.0371	-2.15	0.0666	-1.80	0.0271
	Jan	MK	-1.15	0.1563	-1.93	0.1039	-0.72	0.1334	-3.13	0.0500	-1.84	0.0551
	Feb	MK	-0.82	0.4530	-1.28	0.3170	-0.35	0.3170	-2.06	0.0730	-1.59	0.0666
	Mar	MK	-1.50	0.3376	-1.48	0.2110	-0.47	0.0799	-2.82	0.0606	-1.32	0.0196
	Apr	MK	-0.92	0.4044	-0.96	0.3813	-0.34	0.2603	-2.50	0.1689	-0.77	0.1131
	May	MK	-1.56	0.2603	-1.46	0.3590	-0.10	0.8349	-1.69	0.3170	-0.17	0.6767
	Jun	MK	-0.19	0.8349	-0.77	0.6168	-0.89	0.1962	-1.16	0.4044	-1.70	0.1445
	Jul	MK	0.06	0.8675	-0.82	0.2430	-1.02	0.0010	-1.84	0.0730	-2.75	0.0031
	Aug	MK	0.59	0.1563	-0.48	0.1821	-1.17	0.0003	-2.08	0.0067	-2.88	0.0000
	Sep	MK	0.24	0.5878	-0.37	0.1962	-0.67	0.0015	-2.27	0.0002	-2.72	0.0000
	Oct-Dec	SK	-0.13	0.7001	-0.33	0.2895	-0.34	0.0042	-1.48	0.0010	-1.64	0.0000
	Jan-Mar	SK	-1.19	0.0673	-1.49	0.0237	-0.53	0.0132	-2.67	0.0011	-1.50	0.0004
	Apr-Jun	SK	-0.87	0.2020	-1.09	0.1776	-0.33	0.1234	-1.61	0.0604	-0.69	0.0432
	Jul-Sep	SK	0.33	0.2107	-0.48	0.0268	-0.96	0.0000	-2.09	0.0000	-2.77	0.0000
	Oct-Mar	SK	-0.43	0.1154	-0.66	0.0184	-0.40	0.0002	-1.87	0.0000	-1.59	0.0000
	Apr-Sep	SK	-0.01	0.9932	-0.68	0.0115	-0.73	0.0000	-1.95	0.0000	-2.01	0.0000
Oct-Sep	SK	-0.22	0.2604	-0.66	0.0005	-0.55	0.0000	-1.93	0.0000	-1.76	0.0000	
Annual	MK	-0.67	0.3376	-1.60	0.0606	-0.73	0.0005	-2.95	0.0196	-1.49	0.0018	
Annual	LR	-0.48	0.4462	-1.12	0.0978	-0.65	0.0005	-1.97	0.0421	-1.50	0.0010	
Precipitation	Oct	MK	2.45	0.4283	1.07	0.3590			1.07	0.3590		
	Nov	MK	-1.22	0.2603	-0.58	0.2973			-0.58	0.2973		
	Dec	MK	0.03	1.0000	0.08	1.0000			0.08	1.0000		
	Jan	MK	-2.18	0.2266	-1.31	0.2973			-1.31	0.2973		
	Feb	MK	-1.54	0.4530	-0.67	0.5317			-0.67	0.5317		
	Mar	MK	3.90	0.1689	1.85	0.1334			1.85	0.1334		
	Apr	MK	-1.54	0.3376	-0.46	0.5878			-0.46	0.5878		
	May	MK	0.19	0.9335	0.33	0.7387			0.33	0.7387		
	Jun	MK	-2.34	0.3376	-0.41	0.7387			-0.41	0.7387		
	Jul	MK	-1.92	0.6022	0.19	0.4283			0.19	0.4283		
	Aug	MK	0.00	0.8671	0.24	0.3813			0.24	0.3813		
	Sep	MK	-1.27	0.7543	0.11	0.8349			0.11	0.8349		
	Oct-Dec	SK	-0.29	0.8662	-0.06	0.9616			-0.06	0.9616		
	Jan-Mar	SK	-0.46	0.7361	-0.03	0.9233			-0.03	0.9233		
	Apr-Jun	SK	-1.33	0.2895	-0.18	0.7543			-0.18	0.7543		
	Jul-Sep	SK	-0.73	0.6997	0.20	0.2682			0.20	0.2682		
	Oct-Mar	SK	-0.33	0.7144	-0.05	0.9119			-0.05	0.9119		
	Apr-Sep	SK	-1.02	0.3027	0.11	0.5801			0.11	0.5801		
Oct-Sep	SK	-0.61	0.3205	0.07	0.7589			0.07	0.7589			
Annual	MK	-0.55	0.4283	-0.18	0.8025			-0.18	0.8025			
Annual	LR	-0.29	0.6904	-0.05	0.8975			-0.05	0.8975			

Term	Season	Test	Flow		TP Load		TP Concentration		TN Load		TN Concentration	
			Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value
Evaporation	Oct	MK	-0.74	0.0271								
	Nov	MK	0.20	0.0500								
	Dec	MK										
	Jan	MK										
	Feb	MK										
	Mar	MK	1.28	0.0000								
	Apr	MK	0.39	0.0218								
	May	MK	0.70	0.0666								
	Jun	MK	1.01	0.0013								
	Jul	MK	1.01	0.0001								
	Aug	MK	0.71	0.0086								
	Sep	MK	0.29	0.2603								
	Oct-Dec	SK	0.00	0.8712								
	Jan-Mar	SK	0.00	0.0000								
	Apr-Jun	SK	0.68	0.0000								
	Jul-Sep	SK	0.71	0.0000								
	Oct-Mar	SK	0.00	0.0087								
Apr-Sep	SK	0.68	0.0000									
Oct-Sep	SK	0.00	0.0000									
Annual	MK	0.70	0.0007									
Annual	LR	0.69	0.0002									
Net Inflow	Oct	MK	0.36	0.5594	-0.27	0.5047	-0.47	0.0666	-0.65	0.2603	-1.07	0.0059
	Nov	MK	-0.06	0.8349	-0.20	0.6168	-0.05	0.8025	-1.62	0.0454	-1.32	0.0004
	Dec	MK	0.13	0.9667	-0.22	0.9005	-0.40	0.0500	-1.08	0.1445	-1.29	0.0302
	Jan	MK	-1.36	0.1962	-1.83	0.1563	-0.75	0.0954	-2.75	0.0666	-1.42	0.0666
	Feb	MK	-1.00	0.3376	-1.20	0.2973	-0.36	0.1821	-2.10	0.0730	-1.43	0.0666
	Mar	MK	-1.52	0.3170	-1.33	0.2973	-0.44	0.1821	-2.75	0.0874	-1.08	0.0110
	Apr	MK	-1.28	0.3590	-0.91	0.2783	0.27	0.4044	-2.34	0.1821	-0.50	0.2110
	May	MK	-1.90	0.2266	-1.17	0.3813	0.68	0.2603	-1.64	0.3376	-0.04	0.9335
	Jun	MK	-1.00	0.4283	-0.71	0.5878	0.05	0.9335	-1.10	0.3590	-0.51	0.4530
	Jul	MK	-1.16	0.3813	-0.79	0.1962	0.12	0.9005	-1.39	0.0730	-0.92	0.1689
	Aug	MK	0.43	0.7704	-0.46	0.1962	-0.82	0.1821	-1.67	0.0046	-1.91	0.0059
	Sep	MK	0.43	0.6465	-0.31	0.1962	-0.64	0.0500	-1.83	0.0001	-2.20	0.0000
	Oct-Dec	SK	0.11	0.8098	-0.26	0.4411	-0.32	0.0183	-1.03	0.0075	-1.22	0.0000
	Jan-Mar	SK	-1.29	0.0572	-1.49	0.0407	-0.52	0.0115	-2.41	0.0019	-1.23	0.0003
	Apr-Jun	SK	-1.49	0.0874	-0.96	0.1420	0.33	0.2287	-1.61	0.0604	-0.36	0.2196
	Jul-Sep	SK	-0.04	0.9616	-0.45	0.0237	-0.52	0.0673	-1.68	0.0000	-1.83	0.0000
	Oct-Mar	SK	-0.43	0.2436	-0.59	0.0455	-0.39	0.0005	-1.58	0.0000	-1.22	0.0000
Apr-Sep	SK	-0.59	0.2109	-0.63	0.0081	-0.10	0.6643	-1.66	0.0000	-1.00	0.0000	
Oct-Sep	SK	-0.50	0.0863	-0.62	0.0010	-0.27	0.0057	-1.61	0.0000	-1.15	0.0000	
Annual	MK	-0.98	0.2783	-1.53	0.0730	-0.26	0.1229	-2.72	0.0175	-1.04	0.0005	
Annual	LR	-0.63	0.4090	-1.06	0.1067	-0.42	0.0552	-1.73	0.0512	-1.10	0.0002	

Term	Season	Test	Flow		TP Load		TP Concentration		TN Load		TN Concentration	
			Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value
Lake Outflow	Oct	MK	-0.23	0.7387	-2.19	0.1131	-1.86	0.0606	-1.31	0.2603	-1.14	0.3170
	Nov	MK	0.18	0.9335	-0.92	0.5594	-1.44	0.0551	0.24	0.7075	0.20	0.8675
	Dec	MK	-1.72	0.1689	-2.33	0.1563	-1.04	0.0730	-1.70	0.2603	-0.13	0.7704
	Jan	MK	-3.00	0.0371	-5.68	0.0046	-1.46	0.0302	-4.91	0.0218	0.13	0.8675
	Feb	MK	-2.69	0.4283	-3.90	0.1689	-0.79	0.2110	-3.32	0.2430	0.37	0.6465
	Mar	MK	-2.15	0.3813	-2.38	0.3590	0.70	0.1131	-1.88	0.4785	0.96	0.1962
	Apr	MK	-1.12	0.4530	0.52	0.7387	0.79	0.4044	0.02	1.0000	0.43	0.5878
	May	MK	-0.92	0.4530	0.72	0.6767	1.41	0.0874	-0.95	0.1821	-0.42	0.3590
	Jun	MK	-0.26	0.8025	0.47	0.6168	0.56	0.8349	-1.59	0.0874	-1.93	0.1039
	Jul	MK	0.19	0.7387	2.41	0.0371	1.88	0.0954	0.65	0.3590	0.00	1.0000
	Aug	MK	-0.01	1.0000	1.51	0.0954	1.88	0.0110	0.26	0.8025	-0.02	1.0000
	Sep	MK	0.09	0.8675	-0.70	0.6465	-0.95	0.4283	-1.00	0.3376	-1.00	0.2430
	Oct-Dec	SK	-0.37	0.3478	-1.65	0.0362	-1.31	0.0012	-0.80	0.2787	-0.26	0.5157
	Jan-Mar	SK	-2.68	0.0285	-3.93	0.0028	-0.47	0.2895	-3.23	0.0150	0.41	0.2579
	Apr-Jun	SK	-0.66	0.3006	0.53	0.4555	0.93	0.1068	-0.98	0.0789	-0.42	0.2479
	Jul-Sep	SK	0.08	0.7727	1.18	0.0572	1.15	0.0484	0.05	0.9042	-0.29	0.4851
	Oct-Mar	SK	-0.98	0.0263	-2.50	0.0003	-0.91	0.0022	-1.62	0.0126	0.14	0.7400
	Apr-Sep	SK	-0.14	0.6037	0.87	0.0600	1.03	0.0109	-0.51	0.2506	-0.38	0.1871
	Oct-Sep	SK	-0.44	0.0519	-0.55	0.2264	-0.12	0.7225	-0.90	0.0098	-0.16	0.4889
	Annual	MK	-0.76	0.3376	0.27	0.7075	0.99	0.0500	-1.10	0.1821	-0.02	0.9335
Annual	LR	-0.67	0.3552	0.07	0.9150	0.75	0.1316	-0.74	0.2494	-0.07	0.8704	
Net Retention	Oct	MK			1.72	0.7075			-34.63	0.4044		
	Nov	MK			-4.76	0.1445			-38.29	0.0244		
	Dec	MK			-0.23	0.8675			-0.10	0.9667		
	Jan	MK			-1.99	0.1229			12.22	0.1334		
	Feb	MK			-6.53	0.0018			-12.13	0.1689		
	Mar	MK			-2.76	0.2110			-0.58	0.9335		
	Apr	MK			-2.76	0.2603			5.28	0.1445		
	May	MK			-2.03	0.6465			17.94	0.0500		
	Jun	MK			6.21	0.5594			24.16	0.5878		
	Jul	MK			-30.48	0.0175			-124.61	0.0076		
	Aug	MK			23.06	0.1962			87.20	0.2783		
	Sep	MK			18.24	0.0076			58.18	0.1039		
	Oct-Dec	SK			-2.06	0.4702			-18.64	0.0673		
	Jan-Mar	SK			-3.61	0.0006			0.06	1.0000		
	Apr-Jun	SK			-1.23	0.5634			12.84	0.0208		
	Jul-Sep	SK			6.25	0.3603			0.98	0.9808		
	Oct-Mar	SK			-2.90	0.0031			-6.53	0.1988		
	Apr-Sep	SK			0.50	0.8183			13.19	0.0970		
	Oct-Sep	SK			-2.13	0.0549			1.00	0.7958		
	Annual	MK			-1.07	0.1334			1.78	0.5878		
Annual	LR			-1.23	0.0873			1.29	0.6659			

Term	Season	Test	Flow		TP Load		TP Concentration		TN Load		TN Concentration	
			Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value	Slope (%/yr)	p-value
Lake Mean Storage	Oct	MK					-2.12	0.0335			-1.33	0.1821
	Nov	MK					-1.84	0.0271			0.29	0.7075
	Dec	MK					-1.27	0.0799			0.00	1.0000
	Jan	MK					-1.50	0.0411			0.34	0.5317
	Feb	MK					-0.69	0.3813			0.47	0.5317
	Mar	MK					0.69	0.2603			1.26	0.1563
	Apr	MK					0.80	0.1039			0.40	0.3813
	May	MK					1.58	0.0124			-0.68	0.2783
	Jun	MK					0.13	0.9335			-1.94	0.0500
	Jul	MK					0.91	0.1962			-0.01	1.0000
	Aug	MK					1.40	0.0097			0.15	0.6767
	Sep	MK					-0.20	0.9335			-0.33	0.5878
	Oct-Dec	SK					-1.71	0.0004			-0.22	0.5964
	Jan-Mar	SK					-0.49	0.3006			0.62	0.1177
	Apr-Jun	SK					0.88	0.0141			-0.55	0.2107
	Jul-Sep	SK					0.82	0.0285			-0.02	0.9424
	Oct-Mar	SK					-1.02	0.0012			0.22	0.4694
Apr-Sep	SK					0.87	0.0010			-0.25	0.3448	
Oct-Sep	SK					0.01	0.9760			-0.04	0.8804	
Annual	MK					0.17	0.6465			-0.24	0.7075	
Annual	LR					0.08	0.8281			-0.23	0.5451	
Background Inflows	Oct	MK			-0.18	0.7704			-0.18	0.7704		
	Nov	MK			-0.06	0.9005			-0.06	0.9005		
	Dec	MK			-0.17	0.8349			-0.17	0.8349		
	Jan	MK			-1.15	0.1563			-1.15	0.1563		
	Feb	MK			-0.82	0.4530			-0.82	0.4530		
	Mar	MK			-1.50	0.3376			-1.50	0.3376		
	Apr	MK			-0.92	0.4044			-0.92	0.4044		
	May	MK			-1.56	0.2603			-1.56	0.2603		
	Jun	MK			-0.19	0.8349			-0.19	0.8349		
	Jul	MK			0.06	0.8675			0.06	0.8675		
	Aug	MK			0.59	0.1563			0.59	0.1563		
	Sep	MK			0.24	0.5878			0.24	0.5878		
	Oct-Dec	SK			-0.13	0.7001			-0.13	0.7001		
	Jan-Mar	SK			-1.19	0.0673			-1.19	0.0673		
	Apr-Jun	SK			-0.87	0.2020			-0.87	0.2020		
	Jul-Sep	SK			0.33	0.2107			0.33	0.2107		
	Oct-Mar	SK			-0.43	0.1154			-0.43	0.1154		
Apr-Sep	SK			-0.01	0.9932			-0.01	0.9932			
Oct-Sep	SK			-0.22	0.2604			-0.22	0.2604			
Annual	MK			-0.67	0.3376			-0.67	0.3376			
Annual	LR			-0.48	0.4462			-0.48	0.4462			